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Contributors	Maeva Lavigne Philippot, VUB

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SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract

This deliverable presents a life cycle assessment (LCA) model for evaluating the environmental impacts of onshore and offshore wind turbines across Europe, incorporating regional conditions. As identified in D2.7.a, an existing LCA model used to calculate environmental impacts from on- and offshore wind turbines is used in this work. The model enhances existing LCA approaches by integrating spatially refined parameters such as grid connection cable length, transportation distances, foundation types based on sea depth, and country-specific datasets for installation, operation, and end-of-life phases. Using a functional unit of 1 kWh of electricity, the model is applied to turbines in France, Italy, Norway, Belgium, and Germany. Climate change impacts are assessed through statistical analysis, identifying capacity factors and turbine lifetime as key parameters. Additionally, a geographically differentiated life cycle impact assessment is developed, considering biodiversity impacts based on land use changes. The model has been optimized to reach high computational efficiency, enabling seamless integration into the WIMBY interactive map.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCI	Life cycle inventory
kWh	Kilowatt hour
GWP100	Global Warming Potential
GLO	Global
RoW	Rest of the world
RER	Rest of Europe
CF	Capacity factor(s)
ChF	Characterization factors
E	Electricity production
P	Rated power of a wind turbine
LT	Lifetime of a wind turbine
CC	Climate change
PDF	Potentially disappeared fractions of species
LU	Land use
LUT	Land use type
WT	Wind turbines
LCIA	Life cycle impact assessment
ADP	Material resources: metals/minerals
HT	Human toxicity: carcinogenic organics
OD	Ozone depletion
PA0401	Appenine deciduous montane forests
PA0402	Atlantic mixed forests
PA0405	Baltic mixed forests
PA0406	Cantabrian mixed forests
PA0409	Celtic broadleaf forests and
PA0412	Central European mixed forests
PA0421	English Lowlands beech forests
PA0429	North Atlantic moist mixed forests
PA0431	Pannonian mixed forests
PA0432	Po Basin mixed forests
PA0435	Rodope montane mixed forests
PA0436	Sarmatic mixed forests
PA0445	Western European broadleaf forests
PA0501	Alps conifer and mixed forests

PA0503	Caledon conifer forests
PA0520	Scandinavian coastal conifer forests,
PA0608	Scandinavian and Russian taiga
PA1106	Kola Peninsula tundra
PA1110	Scandinavian Montane Birch forest and grasslands
PA1201	Aegean and Western Turkey sclerophyllous and mixed forests
PA1203	Canary Islands dry woodlands and forests
PA1205	Crete Mediterranean forests
PA1208	Iberian conifer forests
PA1209	Iberian sclerophyllous and semi-deciduous forests
PA1210	Illyrian deciduous forests
PA1211	Italian sclerophyllous and semi-deciduous forests
PA1212	Mediterranean acacia-argania dry woodlands and succulent thickets
PA1222	Tyrrhenian-Adriatic Sclerophyllous and mixed forests
PA1215	Northeastern Spain and Southern France Mediterranean forests an
PA1216	Northwest Iberian montane forests
PA1217	Pindus Mountains mixed forests.
PA1218	South Appenine mixed montane forests
PA1219	Southeastern Iberian shrubs and woodlands
PA1221	Southwest Iberian Mediterranean sclerophyllous and mixed forests
PA1222	Tyrrhenian-Adriatic Sclerophyllous and mixed forests
EoL	End-of-life

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable contains the developed spatially explicit life cycle assessment (LCA) model for onshore and offshore wind turbines. Additionally, methodological contributions on geographically differentiated characterization factors are made by calculating biodiversity impacts due to land use change. This was operationalized based on input data from Task 1.2 Land & Sea Use And Change.

The life cycle assessment model takes the rated power, its geographical location and the annual electricity production as arguments. Other data required for the calculation are in the background of the model, e.g. the ecoinvent database, a bathymetric map, the location of turbine components, a dataset on the electric power buses of the European electricity grid, scientific reports, for example on the dimension, sizes and material quantities of different floating foundations, etc.

Main results are the environmental impacts, modifiable in the function of the model, per kilowatt hour electricity generated and presented per life cycle stage. To demonstrate the model, five case studies are calculated, considering on- and offshore wind turbines. A statistical analysis is included to understand the model's most influential parameters and potential interrelations. Additionally, the biodiversity impacts are calculated for the entire European wind fleet and analyzed within this deliverable.

The model is completed and considerable effort was invested in minimizing its computational requirements, which should facilitate its integration in the WIMBY interactive map.

Since a prospective LCA based on a future energy system depends on input from the recently initiated WP4, the prospective LCA results will be included in D4.6.. However, the impact is minimal, as no other WP relies on the outcome of that assesment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Wind energy holds great promise for the decarbonization of the energy system due to its low climate change impact and cost-competitiveness. Therefore, various life cycle assessment (LCA) models exist for the evaluation of wind power [1]–[3], all taking into account, to some extent, spatial refined life cycle inventory (LCI) data. The current state of literature has been extensively described in deliverable D2.7. Life Cycle Assessment, version a, and thus will not be further discussed in this version.

A model capable of evaluating the environmental impact of potential on- and offshore wind turbines of all Europe is currently lacking. This remains challenging due to its large scope coming along with extensive data.

Therefore, for the first time, we present a LCA model that considers turbines' location all over Europe scalable to its' rated power to produce spatially differentiated results.

The objective of the deliverable is twofold:

- Development of an LCA python package capable of calculating spatially differentiated environmental results of wind turbines at a given location
- Calculation of spatially differentiated environmental impacts for the European wind fleet applying the developed LCA package

Based on this context, the following research questions are formulated:

- What location-specific parameters influence the environmental impacts of wind turbines?
- How can those location-specific parameters be included in an LCA?
- What are the environmental impacts of the European wind fleet applying the newly developed LCA package?

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

LCA is an internationally standardized method to assess environmental impacts of goods and services [4], [5]. LCA method includes 4 steps: goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment and interpretation. In the goal and scope definition, the system boundaries, functional unit and the impact assessment method are defined. The inventory analysis requires the collection of an inventory of inputs and outputs to and from the environment. The impact assessment step focuses on calculating the results, followed by their interpretation.

In this task, besides updating the model “WIND_LCA_DK” [6] with the latest Brightway version 2.5 [7] and ecoinvent cut-off 3.9.1 [8], the LCI dictionary is refined to output impacts per life cycle stage. Environmental Footprint Version 3.1. is used as an impact assessment method [9]. For the WIMBY interactive map, Climate Change, expressed in Global Warming Potential (GWP100), is chosen to be the default impact category. Other impact categories can be calculated easily by modifying the impact category in the argument of the LCA function. The functional unit is set to be 1 kilowatt hour (kWh) delivered electricity.

Two different assessments are presented in this deliverable. First, to show the functionality and output of the developed LCA model, a case study is defined, with an assessment of one onshore and one offshore turbine in Belgium, France, Germany, Italy and Norway. As there are pilot sites in Italy and Norway, those countries are chosen. Germany is added as it has a large and comparable old wind turbine fleet. France is added due to its high share of nuclear power in the electricity mix, and Belgium as it is restricted in space for new wind turbines (both onshore and offshore). To align with the WIMBY interactive map, the rated power of the onshore and offshore turbines are set to 3.4MW and 10MW respectively. For this assessment, the annual electricity production of the turbines is obtained from the WIMBY interactive map.

The second evaluation targets to assess the environmental impacts of the wind fleet at a country level. Therefore, the annual electricity production of the turbines is calculated. The geographical scope of the fleet assessment is partly aligned with the assessment of the individual turbines: results for Belgium, Italy and Norway are presented in section 3.3, supported by an evaluation of the British wind fleet. The British wind fleet is selected as it

represents a good share between on- and offshore wind turbines. The adjusted geographical scope is chosen due to available results at the time when this deliverable was compiled. Additionally, graphical visualization of results for Austria, France, Denmark and Portugal are only added in the ANNEX and not described qualitatively further in the section 3.3.2 as those results became only available after the initial submission to the reviewers. The full approach is described in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview on the two evaluations included in this deliverable. The first evaluation (left side) represents the evaluation of five on- and offshore case studies, whereas the second evaluation (right side) represents a fleet evaluation (AEP = annual electricity production, LCA = life cycle assessment).

2.1 Spatially differentiated environmental impacts

In the context of this deliverable, refined LCI data are explored along with five location-specific parameters are investigated:

1. Type of installation,
2. Foundation type,
3. Distance to the electric power grid,

4. Transport distances and
5. Electricity production of the turbines

The LCA model including their updated location-specific parameters are visualized in Figure 2. The sections hereafter follow the list of location-specific parameters. The type of installation and the foundation type are explained in the same section. As a starting point, the modification of the life cycle inventory model are presented.

Figure 2: System boundaries highlighting improved LCI data collection (source: own depiction).

To integrate the location-specific parameters into the LCA, the following steps are undertaken: First, the location (longitude/latitude) is added as an argument to determine the LCI data of a single turbine. The location data is then used to obtain the following LCI data: a) the ISO country code to identify relevant ecoinvent processes, b) the type of foundation (offshore/onshore), c) the sea depth, d) the cable length and e) the transportation distances.

2.1.1 Life cycle inventory modelling

We build on “WIND_LCA_DK”[6], an open-source model developed to assess the Danish wind turbine fleet producing cradle-to-grave inventory using dynamic scaling functions, and further develop it to assess wind turbines on the European continent [1]. Since its publication in 2019, a new Brightway version was released coming along with improved and additional functionalities. Also, the ecoinvent database 3.9.1. cut-off is introduced as a background database [8]. To update the existing “WIND_LCA_DK” model,

those recent advancements are included in the WIMBY LCA. Furthermore, the presentation of environmental impacts is further refined so the LCA model outputs results per life cycle stage, namely per component production, transport, assembly, maintenance and disposal.

Then, the coordinates are added as arguments in the function to build the LCI. The location is then used to determine the two letter ISO country code. Therefore, a shape file including 258 countries of the world with a resolution of 10 times 10 meters is obtained from Nature Earth and the location of the ISO country code is read [10].

2.1.2 Refinement of inventory data

Considering the different life cycle stages of wind turbines, one recognizes that the activities do not all happen at the installation location of the wind turbines. During the assembly, maintenance and disposal stage, the required materials and activities can be sourced locally, e.g. electricity in the assembly stage. The electricity consumed during the assembly of the wind turbine at its future location is assumed to be sourced from the country where the turbine is installed. Contrary to local sourcing, the material sourcing in the component production stage are unlikely to be supplied locally, but rather originate from a global or European market.

One of the attributes of an ecoinvent dataset is the geographical location, which represents the geographical system boundaries that each dataset represents. In the "WIND_LCA_DK" model, wherever applicable the datasets using geographical reference of Denmark is chosen. In the WIMBY LCA, this is modified and implemented in a variable way. Therefore, a dictionary has been built specifying different geographical areas per life cycle stage (see Figure A26 in the ANNEX). As a result, the location of the datasets in the assembly, maintenance and disposal stage changes if the country of the wind turbine is modified.

2.1.3 Foundation types

For simplicity reasons, this report uses the term foundation simultaneously for on- and offshore installations as the objective is to build a model for both technologies. Various offshore foundations for wind turbines nowadays exist. Their application depends on many criteria, such as sea depth, and type of seabed. According to WindEUROPE, in 2019, over 80% of the European offshore wind turbines have a monopile foundation, followed by a jacket and

gravity-based foundation (9 and 6% respectively of all offshore installations) [11]. Contrary to real installation, the scientific literature focuses on different foundation concepts: Hong et al. (2024) found, that 39% out of 72 scientific publications investigate the concept of spar buoy foundations, 25% of semi-submersible foundations and 16% on barge foundations [12].

As the original “WIND_LCA_DK” model already includes monopile foundation, which can be installed in water depths of up to 30 meters [13], two more offshore foundations are added to the WIMBY LCA model. Thus, the model chooses different foundation types based on the sea depths. The sea depths is chosen as only decision criteria, even though this might not fully present reality. However, as other decision criteria, e.g. types of seabed are more difficult to convert into a parameter that can be included in a simple manner in the LCA function, currently the sea depth serves as only parameter for the selection of offshore foundations.

To use the sea depth as decision criteria for the floating foundations, the sea depths is first obtained using the turbines location and GEBCO’s global gridded bathymetric data sets [14]. Depending on the sea depth, the following offshore foundations are selected for different sea depths:

- 0-30 meters sea depth: monopile
- 30-60 meters sea depth: semi-submersible floating foundation
- Deeper than 60 meters: spar buoy floating foundation

Various studies containing LCI of different offshore floating foundations exist [13], [15], [16]. In coordination with the WIMBY interactive map, which selected for offshore wind turbine installations with a rated power of 10MW, LCI data for semi-submersible floating foundations (semi-sub) and spar buoy floating foundations (spar) are adopted from Garcia-Teruel et al. (2022) [16]. Apart from size similarity, those data are used to model the Hywind and Kincardine offshore wind farm in the North Sea. For the spar, the reported rated power is 9.5MW, whereas the turbine with a semi-sub has a rated power of 6MW. In terms of functionality of the semi-sub, the turbine is mounted on a floating platform, which is attached to the seabed via 4 anchors at a depth of between 60-80 meters. The spar concept is an extension of the turbine tower, similar to a tension leg, filled with a ballast (in this case: iron ore). The spar buoy is fixed to the seabed via three anchors. This floating solution is reported to be in place at sea depths between 95 and 120 meters. Table 1 summarizes the weight used to scale the materials. For both floating foundations, simple scaling functions are defined. The offshore platform is scaled on the rated power, whereas the cable lengths

are based on the sea depth. For the cable length, the material need is estimated to be 0.4 tons/meter for the semi-sub and 0.38 tons/meter for the spar.

Sub-component	Material	Amount installed	Mass (tons)
Semi-submersible floating foundation			
Platform	Steel	1	2,750
Anchors	Steel	4	20
Chains	Steel	4	312
Material intensity	Tons/meter	n.a.	0.4
Spar-buoy floating foundation			
Spar structure	Steel	1	2,300
Ballast	Iron ore	1	5,000
Anchors	Steel	3	100
Chains	Steel	3	273.6
Material intensity	Tons/meter	n.a.	0.38

Table 1: Materials used in the WIMBY LCA for different floating foundations (source: [16]).

2.1.4 Cable lengths

Another parameter depending on the wind turbine is the electric connection of the turbine with the electricity grid. In the original “WIND_LCA_DK”, the cable length is an interpolation between rated power of the turbine, the cable length and the road surface. The distance of the turbine and the next suitable point of the grid, to which it can be connected defines the lengths of the cable, which is accounted for in the LCA model as material requirement (mainly copper and insulation).

This modelling, however, poses two main challenges: first, the right grid connection point needs to be identified. From an electro-technical point of view, various points exist to connect the wind turbines (e.g. high or medium voltage grid) and depend on the size of the wind turbine park. Once the voltage level is identified, the connection point needs to be found. Normally, wind turbines at utility scale level are connected to the electricity grid via substations, which help to distribute and transform voltage, e.g. from high to medium voltage.

Unfortunately, publicly available data for substations including their location (long/lat) or any other power system part that could be used as a proxy is not available. On the Transparency Platform of ENTSO-E, a map of the

European transmission system network containing different voltage levels, connection lines, phase shifter, substation, converter, etc. is available [source ENTSO-E]. However, upon request, the data points on the map are not accessible as it is considered critical infrastructure. Alternatively, data on the transmission system network could have been collected at every single transmission or distribution grid operator in every European country. Within the scope of the task, this approach is unfeasible.

Instead, datasets of a topologically connected presentation of the European high-voltage grid based on OpenStreetMap is consulted [17]. In this public repository, datasets for buses, converters, transformers, etc. are available. In the absence of substations, the electric power buses datasets are used as proxy and for further processing. Electric power buses are nodes connecting several lines including several components, e.g. loads and generators.

With Pandas 'geopy' package, the geodesic distance between the turbine location and the closest power bus is calculated. The geodesic distance is not a straight line between the two points, but takes into account the Earth's curvature. Unconsidered in this calculation remains the elevation (accounting for a difference in topology) between the two points as well as exclusion zones of the electric cables (military territory, airports, natural protected areas, etc.).

2.1.5 Transport distances

In complex product systems such as wind turbines, the various components are not necessarily manufactured at the same site. Reasons for different component production locations can be various, e.g. labor cost, electricity prices, knowledge accumulation, or other strategic arguments. Therefore, reducing the factory-to-site distance to the distance between the turbines' installation and for example the headquarters of the manufacturer would not be justifiable. To represent the component transportation from different manufacturing locations to the turbines' location, the manufacturer database of 'windpower.net' is consulted. The 20 biggest manufacturers of the EU wind fleet are identified according to the number of their installation. As visible in Figure 3, ENERCON and VESTAS are the largest manufacturers in Europe by number of installed turbines and account together for 55% of all installed turbines after removing turbines where no information is available on their manufacturers.

Figure 3: Percentage of total installed EU wind turbines (source: windpower.net)

Afterwards, information from the wind turbine manufacturers’ websites and documents is obtained to identify component manufacturing locations. Enercon and Vestas both disclose more detailed information on the manufacturing location of subcomponents, whereas other manufacturers do not provide further data on sub-component production (see Table 2 and Table 3).

Component	Sub-component	ISO_A2	Address	lon	lat
Rotor	Blades	PT	Av. de Cabo Verde 36, Viana do Castelo, Portugal	-8.85	41.69
Rotor	Blades	TR	10042 Sokak No 12 İAOSB, 35680 Çiğli/İzmir, Türkiye	27.03	38.47
Rotor	Hub	DE	Borsigstraße 15, 26607 Aurich, Germany	7.50	53.51
Nacelle	Generator	DE	August-Bebel-Damm 26, 39126 Magdeburg, Germany	11.68	52.21
Nacelle	Generator	PL	Oświęcimska 102e, 45-641 Opole, Poland	17.96	50.60
Nacelle	Generator	PT	Parque Empresarial de Lanheses, Lanheses, Portugal	-8.63	42.00
Nacelle	Nacelle	DE	Borsigstraße 15, 26607 Aurich, Germany	7.50	53.51
Tower	Tower	DE	Borsigstraße 15, 26607 Aurich, Germany	7.50	53.51

Table 2: Location of sub-component manufacturing according to Enercon (source: Enercon website)

Component	Sub-component	ISO_A2	Address	lon	lat
Rotor	Blades	DK	Vingevej 1, 4900 Nakskov, Denmark	11.12	54.83
Rotor	Blades	DK	Smed Hansensvej 19, 6940 Lem, Denmark	8.38	56.02
Nacelle	Nacelles	DK	E.F. Jacobsensvej 3, 6950 Ringkøbing, Denmark	8.24	56.09
Nacelle	Nacelles	DK	Lindø Sydvej 21, 5330 Munkebo, Denmark	10.54	55.47
Nacelle	Nacelles	DK	Smed Sorensens Vej 5, 6950 Ringkøbing, Denmark	8.24	56.09
Nacelle	Generator	DE	Henry-Koch-Str. 9-13, 23570 Travemünde, Germany	10.84	53.93
Rotor	Blades	IT	Via Ludovico Ariosto, 12, 74100 Taranto, Italy	17.38	40.45
Rotor	Blades	ES	Avda de los Vientos, num. 22, 13520, Daimiel, Spain	-3.61	39.07
Rotor	Blades	GB	West Medina Mills, Stag Lane, Newport, PO30 5TR Isle of Wight, United Kingdom	-1.30	50.72
Tower	Tower	ES	Parque Empresarial Principado de Asturias, 33400 Avilés, Asturias, Spain	-5.92	43.55
Tower	Tower	PL	GSG Towers, Marynarki Polskiej 87, 80-557 Gdańsk, Poland	18.60	54.39
Tower	Tower	UK	CS Wind UK, Machrihanish Business Park, Campbeltown, PA28 6NU, Scotland, United Kingdom	-5.70	55.44
Tower	Tower	DK	Welcon, Bøgekildevej 5, 7323 Give, Denmark	9.25	55.84

Table 3: Location of sub-component manufacturing according to Vestas (source: Vestas website)

A simple function is defined to identify the shortest, accumulated distance of all the components from the turbine location. If a component can be manufactured at more than one facility, the one closest to the wind turbine location is chosen. Distance for rotor, nacelle and tower are kept variable, while for the foundation it is kept static (50 km).

2.1.6 Electricity production

The electricity production used in this assessment are obtained in two different ways: for the interactive map, the electricity production is obtained from the WIMBY map directly. No own calculations of annual electricity production for the case studies is done. Thus, the presented values in Table

4 are directly extracted from the WIMBY interactive map. The locations are randomly chosen on the WIMBY map and do not represent real installations. Instead, those case studies are intended to depict potential wind turbines. A summary of the obtained information for the selected case studies is presented in Table 4.

	Rated power	AEP	Capacity factor	Lon	Lat
Unit	MW	GWh	%		
Onshore					
France	3.4	10.3	35	-1.63	48.16
Italy	3.4	5.7	19	14.42	41.03
Norway	3.4	6.4	22	5.75	58.61
Germany	3.4	8.8	30	10.54	48.02
Belgium	3.4	9.7	33	4.39	51.09
Offshore					
France	10	49	56	-3.65	48.74
Italy	10	40.5	46	11.93	36.78
Norway	10	44.2	50	10.22	59.20
Germany	10	53.4	61	8.53	53.94
Belgium	10	51.6	56	2.65	51.18

Table 4: Electricity data obtained from the WIMBY map. Locations do not reflect real wind turbine installations, but are read out from the WIMBY map manually (AEP = annual electricity production).

For the evaluation of the European wind fleet, the electricity production is calculated independently. The electricity production is used to normalize the environmental impacts, in particular to express results in the functional unit per kilowatt hour produced electricity. With the WIMBY project, the electricity production is obtained for each single turbine in two different ways: for the integration of the LCA into the interactive map, data on the corresponding electricity production is provided by WPI. This data represents the annual production, but as the scope of this assessment is set to represent cradle-to-grave and thus covering the entire turbines' life, the annual electricity production is multiplied over its lifetime. Under section 2.2, an approach to assess the impact of the lifetime on the environmental impacts is presented. For the spatially differentiated results of the European wind fleet, the electricity production of every turbine is calculated. Again, the objective of this calculation is not to determine results representing the exact electricity

production of every turbine. Instead, the results are used to normalize the environmental impact of all EU wind turbines. Even though the calculated electricity production does not reflect exactly the real electricity production per turbine, using this results in the normalization still allows valuable insights into the environmental impacts per turbine. It is important to highlight, that the calculations are just an approximation and do not represent real electricity production of the EU wind turbine fleet.

Within the scope of the project, two important sources are made available: an updated register of all European wind turbines and average wind speed data including bias correction [18], [19]. This data is used to calculate the spatially differentiated electricity production in combination with the power curves of each turbine. In general, power curves represent particular design characteristics of each turbine, vary from turbine to turbine and are mainly commercially available. Similar to the updated register of the European wind turbines, no complete register of power curves of all European wind turbines exists. In a recent publication, Saint-Drenan et al. (2020) developed a parametric model for wind turbine power curves [20]. Based on rated power and rotor diameter, the model provides the power output of wind turbines per wind speed. The cut-in wind speed is set to 3 m/s, whereas the cut-off wind speed is 25 m/s. Based on the provided EU wind turbine register, the power curves of every wind turbine is determined considering each wind turbines rated power and rotor diameter. Turbine-specific cut-in and cut-off wind speeds of every single EU wind turbine are neglected. As identified in previous literature, a cut-in wind speed of 3 m/s with 90% of all wind turbines available in the commercial database provided by windpower.net is identified [20]. The highest distribution of the same wind turbines for the cut-off wind speeds is 25 m/s with 70% [20]. Thus, those cut-in and cut-off wind speeds are adopted in this study as they are found to be a good representation of those commercial dataset for power curves.

Next, the wind speed data are obtained and corrected with the bias-correction file accounting for circumstances reducing the wind speeds. As wind speed data is available at heights of 50, 100 and 200 meters, the hub height of the EU wind turbines are rounded up or off to the closest matching wind speed height. Also, the coordinates of the EU wind turbines are rounded to the nearest 0.25 grid point to match the raster data of the ERA5 data. Then, the corrected wind speed data is retrieved for every wind turbine at the given height for every hour of each month.

Finally, the power output of each turbine can be obtained using the retrieved average wind speed data. As the wind speed data represents average values of 24 hours over 12 months, the power output is then multiplied by 30 days/month and summed up to obtain the annual electricity production. To validate the calculated lifetime electricity production, the capacity factors (CF – used simultaneously as singular and plural within this report) are determined using equation (1):

$$CF_T = \frac{E_{T,LT}}{P_T * 24 * 12 * 30 * LT_T} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- CF_T is the capacity factor of the wind turbine T (%),
- $E_{T,LT}$ is the lifetime electricity production of the wind turbine T (kWh),
- P_T is the rated power of the wind turbine T (kW) and
- LT_T is the lifetime of the wind turbine T (years).

To have some validation of the obtained CF, the average CF of the EU onshore and offshore wind fleet in 2022 of 24% and 34% are consulted [21]. Whenever the obtained CF exceed a certain ‘threshold level’, the CF are manually corrected. This step is undertaken to limit the uncertainty brought along with using a static model for power curves neglecting individual conditions of wind turbines. On the one hand, this approach limits the full environmental advantageous compared to other energy technologies, but it also limits data gaps or data collection errors. Obviously, this step introduces the subjectivity of the researchers or the existing EU wind fleet to the presented results and can be thus understood as a rather conservative approach towards determining the electricity production of the EU wind fleet. Again, the determination electricity production of the EU wind fleet is not supposed represent real electricity production, but rather an approximation. Whenever the calculated CF for onshore turbines exceeds 40%, the European average CF of 24% is applied [21] and the lifetime electricity is recalculated with the average CF. The CF for offshore wind turbines are limited to 50%, and whenever higher values are obtained, the average CF for offshore wind turbines of 34% [21] is applied to recalculate the electricity production with a modified equation (1). The CF obtained from the WIMBY interactive maps remain unchanged to still show the influence of a high CF (in case it exceeded the averages) on the model’s output. For further validation, the lifetime electricity production is calculated based on

the average onshore and offshore CF for all European wind turbines considering 20 and 30 years lifetime.

The evaluation of the wind fleet is done per country and results are included for the countries which are selected as case studies. For the evaluation, the following methodology is applied:

The first step towards understanding the relationship between turbine parameters and total climate change impact was to assess the correlation between individual parameters and the impact results. This initial analysis helped identify potential dependencies and provided insights into how strongly each parameter is associated with variations in climate change impact.

Following this, a regression analysis is conducted to quantify these relationships more precisely. By modeling the total climate change impact as a function of key turbine characteristics like rated power, hub height, rotor diameter, longitude, latitude, CF, and turbine age, the regression allowed for a better understanding of how these parameters contribute to the overall climate change (CC) impacts of wind turbines. This step is important in evaluating the predictive power of each feature and identifying linear or non-linear trends.

As a final step, a feature importance analysis is performed using a Random Forest model. This approach helps identifying the relative influence of each parameter on the total climate change impact by considering complex, nonlinear interactions that may not be fully captured in traditional regression models. The aim of the feature importance rankings is to prioritize the most significant factors driving the results.

2.2 Sensitivity analysis

The influence of the lifetime on the LCA model is further investigated by modifying the currently applied lifetime of 20 years to a minimum of 18 years and a maximum of 30 years. The lower value represent the median lifetime of the Danish wind fleet between 1977 and 2016 [6]. The upper value of 30 years could represent a future lifetime of new wind turbines. Next to the lifetime, the impact of grid connection is evaluated. Instead of using electric power buses dataset, the transformer dataset is used. To evaluate the uncertainty in the background database, a Monte-Carlo simulation with 1,000 samples is conducted. As the model for on- and offshore uses the same background data and the same distributions, the results of the Monte-

Carlo simulation are only presented for onshore turbines. The Monte-Carlo simulation is conducted only for onshore turbines as most of the offshore materials are also included in the onshore turbines. Thus, the onshore Monte-Carlo simulation can be seen as an approximation of the offshore Monte-Carlo simulation too.

2.3 Methodological advancements for geographically differentiated characterization factors

2.3.1 Land use

The impact of wind energy deployment on biodiversity mostly originates from habitat loss and disturbance [22]. The indicator for ecosystem quality in LCA is expressed in potentially disappeared fractions of species (PDF). Characterization factors (ChF) for occupation are in PDF/m² and in PDF·yr/m² for transformation, as recommended by the Life Cycle Initiative, hosted by UN Environment Programme [23].

The assessment of the land use (LU) impact on biodiversity necessitates spatial differentiation, as in each ecoregion, the different present species have different affinity with different LU types and intensities. To be able to assess the LU impact of wind turbines (WT), detection of LU change thanks to satellite data is necessary, as done by BOKU in WPI. Indeed, May et al. [24] use 0.3 ha/MW for direct land use change surface area, originating from a study by NREL from 2009 on the USA wind fleet [25].

However, the integration process of the detected LU change data into LCA does not come without some datatype harmonization problems. One example is the mismatch between the LU types in life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) and satellite data. Scherer et al. (recommended by GLAM) [26] include 16 LU types and intensity while there are 44 LU types in European Corinne dataset [27]. ChF of Scherer et al. cover five species groups (plants, amphibians, birds, mammals, and reptiles) and five broad LU types (cropland, pasture, plantations, managed forests, and urban land) at three intensity levels (minimal, light, and intense). ChF are chosen for global species loss and grouped for all species groups. Another example is the absence of the required biosphere flows to integrate Scherer et al. LCIA method in Brightway. New biosphere flows are created for the five LU types and the three intensity level.

To assess the impacts of LU on biodiversity, the developed model needs the WT location as user input (Figure 4). First, the LU type before the installation

of the WT is identified. To do so, the Corinne Land Cover 2018 100mx100m dataset is consulted, to identify the LU type which is changed.

Figure 4: Flow chart. (LUT= land use type, ChF = characterization factor, LCIA = life cycle impact assessment, WT= wind turbine).

Second, for each ecoregion of Europe [28], LU type from Corinne dataset and LU type and intensity data from Scherer et al. (2023) are compared. Each pixel of Corinne map is compared to each pixel of Scherer et al.’s map. These co-occurrence matrices are normalized to the total number of pixels of the eco-region. The LU types with the maximum co-occurrence are then considered as matched and used to include the ecoregion ChF.

Third, the surface area change of European WT fleet from BOKU is used. Correlation between this area and WT capacity, hub height, or rotor diameter are evaluated. No correlation between change area and WT parameters could be found (See Annex 3). As a result, the average surface change per country is used. The definition of surface area change here is the directly impacted area, which is usually only a small percentage area of a total wind farm area.

In the final step, the LU change due to construction of road is included. Therefore, the legal minimal distance to road for construction of new WT in

European countries is used. For occupation, the lifetime of the WT is used. To compare the impacts over lifecycle stages, the impact on biodiversity needs to be calculated with a compatible method. For this, the method from Scherer et al. (2023) as modified for GLAM is used [29].

3. RESULTS

The calculation speed for determining the impact of a single wind turbine is about 30 seconds, after code optimization. This will facilitate the integration of the developed LCA model into the WIMBY interactive map.

The developed LCA model presents spatially differentiated environmental impacts. Five spatial criteria are introduced to allow those assessment: foundation types, distances to the next grid connection costs, transportation, adjusted ecoinvent datasets and the electricity production. Table 5 summarizes the difference of the spatial criteria of the five case studies. This section will discuss the influence of those data on the environmental impacts of the different case studies.

Case study	Sea depth	Foundation type	Distance to grid	Truck transport
Unit	meter	Text	km	tkm
FR_onshore	n.a.	n.a.	3.08	1,227,000
FR_offshore	23	Monopile	18.12	3,368,000
IT_onshore	n.a.	n.a.	6.32	1,641,000
IT_offshore	303	Spar buoy	131.04	4,937,000
NO_onshore	n.a.	n.a.	7.59	1,071,000
NO_offshore	18	Monopile	34.59	2,821,000
DE_onshore	n.a.	n.a.	18.31	1,316,000
DE_offshore	17	Monopile	16.02	2,387,000
BE_onshore	n.a.	n.a.	8.43	1,169,000
BE_offshore	4	Monopile	19.73	3,159,000

Table 5: Output of the calculated parameters used to spatially differentiate the environmental impacts. Values of truck transport is rounded up or off on thousands of ton kilometers for better readability.

Furthermore, the ISO country code is used to look up the ecoinvent dataset for the given wind turbine installation for activities during the assembly, maintenance or disposal stage of the wind turbine. Figure A27 and Figure A28 in the ANNEX show the ecoinvent datasets, which are available for a given country. The only two activities available on a country level are the electricity mix and waste polypropylene datasets. Other activities represent a European or global scope and are not available on a national level.

3.1 Onshore wind turbine impacts

Before going into details, it is important to stress, that the following results of the case studies presented in section 3.1 and 3.2 are representing a very specific location and thus cannot be generalized to other locations or assumed as representative installation in a given country. To not only look into the impact of CC, material resources: metals/minerals (ADP), human toxicity: carcinogenic organics (HT) and ozone depletion (OD) is analyzed. A first general observation is that the component production stage is the main contributor in all categories, accounting for at least 57% in OD and up to 85% in HT, followed by the assembly, transport, disposal and maintenance (Figure 5). This observation however is not new and has been identified already in previous studies [6]. Reason for the high impact of the component production stage are straightforward: it includes the extraction of all materials to build the separate components of the wind turbines. The contribution of the assembly phase in this study is the second largest contributor as it includes the processing of the extracted materials, e.g. copper wire drawing, and steel, aluminum and chromium sheet rolling.

Figure 5: Contribution of different life cycle stages of onshore wind turbines to climate change, material resources, human toxicity and ozone depletion.

Figure 6 shows the CC impacts of onshore wind turbines of the component which are improved by regionalized LCI data, namely the power supply (cable length), transport (transportation distances) and the electricity used for final assembly of the wind turbines. As the chart points out, the contribution of the regionalized components is, compared to the remaining CC impacts occurring over the lifetime of the turbines, rather small. Out of the parts that are improved with regionalized LCI data, the transportation has the largest influence. Figure 6 also demonstrates very well that there is, even though it might be limited compared to other impacts, a difference between the components improved by regionalized LCI data.

Figure 6: Contribution of the components which are improved by including regionalized LCI data for the onshore case studies.

3.1.1 Impacts of the component production stage

As all the impacts amongst different categories point out the component production stage as the main contributor, the focus of this section is on the CC of the component production stage and conclude with a comparison of the total life cycle stage impacts. Due to the scaling functions of the LCA model, the distribution of the CC remains the same for all five case studies (Figure 7). With 36% CC of the component production stage, the tower is the component with the highest contribution, followed by the nacelle, the rotor

and the foundation, accounting for 26, 22 and 15% of the CC in the component production stage. Electronics and Power supply hardly contribute to CC (up to 2%).

Figure 7: Breakdown of the Climate Change of the component production stage per component for onshore wind turbines.

Again, similar findings have been made before in literature. The foundation, tower, rotor, nacelle and electronics make up all more or less the same share of the total CC impacts compared all the case studies. However, the total CC still vary from case study to case study: As the only regional LCI component, power supply, is found to have a negligible impact, the only distinctive parameter remains the electricity yield of the different turbines. The electricity yield is not directly modeled as component, but used to normalize the total CC impacts, and thus not visible in Figure 7. The CC of the 3.4MW onshore wind turbines are 11, 20, 18, 13 and 12 g CO₂eq/kWh for the case studies in France, Italy, Norway, Germany and Belgium respectively. When looking at the CF, calculated based on the electricity yield, of the case studies, they show similar trends than the CC: for the wind turbines in France, Italy, Norway, Germany and Belgium, a CF of 35, 19, 22, 30 and 33% is used.

Thus, one can conclude that the calculated CC proves, that the model is able to capture spatially differentiated conditions of the wind turbines.

3.1.2 Land use

The different onshore use cases are located in different ecoregions, except for the French and Belgian use cases, both situated in the Atlantic mixed forests ecoregion (Table 6).

Use case	Ecoregion code	Ecoregion name	Pre-installation LU type
France	PA0402	Atlantic mixed forests	Complex cultivation patterns
Italy	PA1222	Tyrrhenian-Adriatic Sclerophyllous and mixed forests	Natural grasslands
Norway	PA0608	Scandinavian and Russian taiga	Coniferous forest
Belgium	PA0402	Atlantic mixed forests	Transitional woodland-shrub
Germany	PA0445	Western European broadleaf forests	Pastures

Table 6: Ecoregions of the use cases

The co-occurrence matrix of these ecoregions can be found in Annex 4. The impact of LU of the onshore use cases reveals that spatial differentiation is of utmost importance as the impact diverges by two orders of magnitude: from 2.9E-8 PDF/GWh for the German use case to 2.9E-6 PDF/GWh for the Italian use case (Figure 8). The ChF for the transformation to urban LU type are about 3 times higher in Tyrrhenian-Adriatic Sclerophyllous and mixed forests ecoregion than in the other ecoregions assessed. In Norway the surface area change is 2 to 4 times higher than in the other countries under study, explaining why this use case shows the second highest impact. Also, the use cases where natural landscapes are modified in opposition to agricultural landscapes show higher impacts. Transformation in all cases represents at least 67% of the impact of the use case. However, the EoL is not included and thus, potential recovery of the LU is not considered. The results of our assessment are in line with other studies assessing the LU impact on biodiversity of WT [22], [24].

Figure 8: Impact of land use on biodiversity for the 4 onshore use cases (PDF = potentially disappeared fractions of species).

3.2 Offshore wind turbine impacts

The offshore wind turbine in Italy has highest impacts in all four assessed impact categories (see Figure 9). Again, the presented results represent a specific location and do not represent the countries average fleet impact. The component manufacturing stage of the Italian wind turbine alone, accounting for 16 g CO₂eq/kWh, is as high as the total CC impact of offshore turbines in the other countries. This trend can be observed for all four impact categories (Figure 9). The main impacts of the Italian offshore turbine originate from the component production stage, followed by assembly and transport. For wind turbines installed in France, Norway, Germany and Belgium, the contribution of life cycle stage is similar. As identified in section 3.1., the CF are a parameter significantly influencing the environmental impacts. However, with CF of 56, 46, 50, 61 and 56% for 10MW offshore wind turbines installed in France, Italy, Norway, Germany and Belgium, the difference between them, e.g. Norway and Italy of only 4% does not justify alone an almost four-fold increase of environmental impacts. As most impacts occur in the component production stage, the next section focuses on exploring the main contributing components of this stage.

Figure 9: Contribution of different life cycle stages of offshore wind turbines to climate change, material resources, human toxicity and ozone depletion.

The most dominant finding of Figure 10 is the high CC impact of the spar buoy foundation in the Italian offshore turbine, which accounts for nearly half of all CC impacts. Similarly, the improvements brought by regionalized LCI data have a greater impact on offshore turbines than on onshore one: all improvements result in, as compared to the full life cycle of the turbines, low contribution to total CC impacts. Amongst those improvements, transportation accounts for the largest share of CC impacts. Figure 10 shows that even when parts are improved with regionalized LCI data, there is still a notable difference in every location, which justifies the effort spent on improving data collection.

Figure 10: Contribution of the components which are improved by including regionalized LCI data for the offshore case studies.

3.2.1 Impacts of the component production stage

For the offshore wind turbines installed in France, Norway, Germany and Belgium, most CC impacts are related to material extraction for the nacelle, the tower and the rotor, making up a maximum of 40, 32 and 24% of CC impacts. At sea depths of 23, 18, 17 and 4 meters, monopiles are selected for the installations in France, Norway, Germany and Belgium and it's CC impact accounts for 2-3% of the component production stage. The power supply and electronics have with 2% or less very little contribution to CC impacts.

The CC impact in the component production stage of the Italian wind turbine stand out in particular of Figure 11: More than 55% of all CC impacts are due to the spar buoy foundation. With a sea depth of 303 meters, not only the spar buoy structure and it's ballast is responsible for those impacts, but also the chains to attach the turbine to the seabed. Regardless of a CF of 46%, the Italian offshore wind turbine has considerable higher CC impact than other installations.

Figure 11: Breakdown of the Climate Change of the component production stage per component for offshore wind turbines.

Overall, the results demonstrate that while some environmental impacts of wind turbines follow general trends, others are highly influenced by location-specific factors. Across all case studies, the component production stage consistently emerges as the main contributor to CC, ADP, HT, and OD, aligning with findings from previous literature. However, the magnitude of these impacts varies significantly, particularly in deep-sea installations that require spar-buoy floating foundations, as exemplified by the Italian offshore case study. Since spar-buoy floaters are still an emerging technology, the limited available data primarily originate from pilot projects with low technology readiness levels, which may not fully reflect production at an industrial scale. To identify the drivers of environmental impacts and the most influential parameters, the following sections focus on analyzing statistical relationships between individual parameters and their effects at the country fleet level.

3.3 Environmental impacts of the EU wind fleet

3.3.1 Electricity production

After the calculation, some harmonization is required. First, 6,166 wind turbines older than 35 years are removed, resulting in total number of 78,322 turbines installed in Europe until November 2021 based on an internal dataset compiled by DTU. Out of the total installed turbines, roughly 7% are offshore and 93% are onshore installations. The electricity production calculation based on wind speeds and power curves resulted for about 67% of offshore turbines in CF greater than 50% and for 2% in a CF smaller than 24%. The electricity production for offshore turbines with those CF outliers are recalculated using the average CF of offshore turbines in 2022 of 34%.

For onshore turbines, 8% of the turbines resulted in a CF higher than 40%, whereas 63% the calculated electricity production resulted in CFs smaller than 14%. Again, the electricity production is modified for onshore wind turbines within such outlying CFs using the average European CF for onshore wind turbines in 2022 of 24%. After the harmonization of the electricity production calculation, the mean CF of off- and offshore wind turbines in Europe are 36% and 23% respectively. Due to the high number of turbines for which the electricity production was modified, the mean CF are very close to the average reported CFs. Thus, the average lifetime electricity production of onshore and offshore European wind turbines is 75 and 293 GWh. Consequently, adding the production of all wind turbines results in an annual electricity production of 352,155 GWh.

Figure 12 shows a large number of outliers and with increasing rated power a large distribution of lifetime electricity production up to at least 5MW installed power. In fact, almost all onshore turbines (99.7%) are below 5MW, which is visible in low range of electricity production from 7MW onwards.

Figure 12: Lifetime electricity production per rated power of the European onshore wind turbines.

Contrary to onshore electricity production data, the calculated electricity production data of offshore turbines spread less due to a lower number of offshore turbines (see Figure 13). In terms of rated power, 60% of the offshore installations are of 5MW rated power or below. Out of the 40% offshore turbines with a rated power greater than 5MW, only 3% were installed since more than 10 years.

Figure 13: Lifetime electricity production per rated power of the European offshore wind turbines.

After adjustment of the calculations with the average CFs, the calculated electricity production lies within the lower end of the theoretical electricity production. This is mainly due to the high amount of adjusted electricity production (55,194 out of 78,322 turbines). One shortcoming with respect to the lifetime production is the aging process of the wind turbines and the associated loss in efficiency, resulting in a decreasing CF over time. Various factors influence this degradation process, e.g. wind speeds, frequency of maintenance, component replacement, etc. Nevertheless, using a theoretical minimum and maximum lifetime of 20 and 30 years highlights still the potential for electricity production due to increased lifetime. The theoretical minimum and maximum electricity production for onshore and offshore turbines along with the own calculated and adjusted results are visualized in Figure A29 and Figure A30 in Annex 5.

Finally, Figure 14 shows the spatially representation of the harmonized electricity production data of the European wind fleet. Regarding electricity production, no huge difference in terms of electricity production becomes visible on the European mainland, represented by a similar purple shade of most dots. Some onshore wind turbines along coastal areas, e.g. in Norway are colored in lighter purple, standing for higher electricity production. A distinction in electricity production is shown for offshore installations: offshore wind turbines in the North Sea show the highest electricity yield. The map does not show turbines in the Mediterranean Sea. In mountain areas (Alps, Pyrenees), very few wind turbines are installed.

Figure 14: Lifetime electricity production of the European wind fleet (source: own calculations).

3.3.2 Climate change impacts

For readability, tables with statistical data are provided in the ANNEX. Data is provided per analyzed country. All figures are available in the ANNEX.

Belgium

The first observation is, that there are considerably less offshore turbines installed than onshore (816 onshore vs. 401 offshore). The CC impact distribution for onshore turbines follows almost a normal distribution while the distribution of offshore turbine impacts is not normally distributed, but concentrated with two groups below 10 and 15 g CO₂eq/kWh and others with an impact around 20 g CO₂eq/kWh or higher. The average CC of the Belgium

onshore wind fleet is 17 g CO₂eq/kWh, following a normal Gaussian distribution curve (Figure 15), whereas the CC impact of the Belgian offshore wind fleet is with 13 g CO₂eq/kWh lower.

Figure 15: Histogram of Climate Change Impacts of on- and offshore wind turbines in Belgium.

The focus of the correlation visualized in the heatmap is on the technical parameters and their relationship with the CC impacts. The first observation is that there are no extremely high correlations between the CC impacts (component production, assembly, transport, maintenance, disposal and total) and the technical parameters. The strongest influence, all below 0.4 though, on the total CC have the hub height, longitude and lifetime electricity production, whereas other parameters have a small to low influence. The influence of the parameters that are regionalized, e.g. sea depth, cable length and transportation distances on the component production stage is represented indirectly via the geographical location (longitude/latitude). With correlations between 0.34 and -0.21, the longitude and latitude shows limited influence on the total results. On the disposal, a medium positive influence is observed, for the lifetime electricity production and the diameter. Contrary, a negative influence is observed for transportation on the disposal impacts. The correlation between technical parameters seems to be very logical, e.g. rated power strongly influences the rotor diameter and the lifetime electricity production (correlation factors of 0.93 and 0.96) and vice versa (Figure A39).

Next, the results of the regression model of the CC impact of the Belgium wind fleet explains 43.4% of the variation in total CC impact ($R^2=0.434$). The model is statistically significant (F-statistic = 154.5, $p < 0.001$). All predictor variables show statistically significant relationships with the dependent variable ($p < 0.001$). The component coefficients suggest that increases in rated power, hub height, rotor diameter, Longitude, and Latitude positively influence the total CC impact, while the lifetime electricity production has a negative effect. Notably, the lifetime electricity production has the strongest effect ($t = -18.849$), while Longitude and Latitude have smaller, yet still significant, influences (Figure A47).

Finally, the random forest model of the CC impacts of Belgium identifies longitude, lifetime electricity production and hub height as most relevant parameter. Latitude and rated power are rated lower compared to the other three parameters (Figure A61).

Norway

The Norwegian wind fleet presents a special case, as almost all turbines in Norway are installed onshore (853 out of 856). With an average of 15 g CO₂eq/kWh, the CC impact of the Norwegian onshore fleet is below e.g. the Belgian onshore wind fleet. Apart from the turbines with a CC impact of around 15 g CO₂eq/kWh, a second group of onshore turbines seem to have impacts of around 28 g CO₂eq/kWh (approximately 80 turbines – see Figure A32). One observation is, that those turbines have a CF of 25 or below (see Figure A55). Contrary to observations in other countries, the total CC impacts of the offshore wind fleet in Norway is with 19 g CO₂eq/kWh above the total CC impact of the onshore wind fleet.

Next, to understand how the model works, the correlation between technical parameters and the results per life cycle stage and also total CC impacts are analyzed (Figure A40). A first observation is that no correlation above/below ± 0.80 is observed. However, hub height and rotor diameter are found to have strong correlations with the total results (0.71 and 0.53). Similar trends of strong positive influences can be observed for the individual life cycle stages, apart from maintenance having strong negative correlations with the design parameters and lifetime electricity production. This could be linked to the size of the turbine: the smaller the turbine, the less maintenance impact. Reasonable interdependencies can be observed for the technical

parameters, e.g. the rated power strongly influences rotor diameter, electricity production and hub height. Longitude and latitude are found to have low correlations with the total impacts (0.11 and -0.03 of longitude and latitude on the total), apart from the disposal stage (-0.63 and -0.62 for longitude and latitude).

The regression model of the Norwegian wind fleet demonstrates a much stronger explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.901$), which can be linked to the fact, that the fleet consists of mainly onshore turbines. The model is statistically significant (F-statistic = 1281, $p < 0.001$). Among the predictor variables, rated power, hub height, rotor diameter and lifetime electricity production show strong and statistically significant associations with the total CC ($p < 0.001$). The Longitude variable is marginally significant ($p = 0.079$), while Latitude has a small but significant negative effect ($p = 0.012$). The lifetime electricity production variable has the largest effect size ($t = -51.261$), indicating a strong negative impact on Total. In contrast, hub height and rotor diameter positively contribute to the total CC, highlighting the importance of turbine design parameters (Figure A48).

Hub height is by far, identified by the random forest model as, the most relevant feature, where lifetime electricity production and rated power follow, however with less low importance. Longitude, latitude and rotor diameter are presented as features with low importance (Figure A62).

Italy

Similar to the Norwegian wind fleet, the Italian wind fleet consists of only onshore turbines. When analyzing the Italian wind turbine fleet, the CC impacts can be grouped into three main groups: most turbines have a CC impact of below 15 g CO₂eq/kWh, a second group has CC impacts between 15 and 17.5 g CO₂eq/kWh and the last group of turbines between 17.5 and 20 g CO₂eq/kWh (Figure A33). This results in an average CC impact of the Italian wind turbines of 13 g CO₂eq/kWh.

The results of the correlation analysis presented in the heatmap (Figure 16) point out some interesting interrelations. In general, rotor diameter, hub height, rated power and lifetime electricity production have a strong to moderate influence on each other, but also on CC impacts. Contrary, the exact position of the wind turbines (long- and latitude) has limited influence. A similar trend can be observed on the influence of the technical

parameters on the CC impacts. The maintenance and disposal stage are an exception, where low to moderate, negative influence is observed for the maintenance stage and low influence for the disposal stage.

Figure 16: Correlation between Climate Change impacts (here represented in the columns/rows Component production, Assembly, Transport, Maintenance, Disposal and Total) for onshore wind turbines in Italy.

The regression model of the Italian wind fleet shows a high explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.923$), indicating that the selected variables effectively capture variations in total CC impact. The model is statistically significant (F-statistic = 8246, $p < 0.001$). All predictor variables contribute significantly to the model ($p < 0.05$). Rotor diameter and lifetime electricity production are highest, with the rotor diameter showing a strong positive association ($t = 104.168$) and lifetime electricity production indicating a strong negative association ($t = -57.284$). The rated power, hug height, and Longitude variables also show strong positive effects. (Figure A49).

The random forest model for the wind turbine fleet of Italy points out the rotor diameter as the most important parameter. Second, but with considerably lower importance comes the lifetime electricity production. The relative

importance of all other parameters is much lower, compared to the rotor diameter (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Feature importance of predictors in the Random Forest model, showing the relative contribution of each variable to the model's predictive power for Italy (units: dimensionless).

Great Britain

The analysis of the CC impacts is extended to the British wind fleet due to its comparably large size of on- and offshore turbines, in particular 5,248 onshore and 2,245 offshore wind turbines. The majority of the onshore turbines is calculated to have a CC impact of below 20 g CO₂eq/kWh, with an average of 13 g CO₂eq/kWh. Comparing CC impacts of on- and offshore wind turbines of Great Britain highlights lower CC impacts of offshore compared to onshore installations (see Figure A31). Indeed, the average CC impact of offshore wind turbines is 12 g CO₂eq/kWh, whereas the total CC impact of the onshore wind turbines is slightly above the offshore turbines, namely 13 g CO₂eq/kWh. One reason for better performance of offshore compared to onshore turbines are higher CF of the offshore fleets (see Figure 18). Another observation becomes evident from Figure 18: the data point towards a negative correlation between CF and CC impacts, which is reasonable given the fact that absolute CC impacts are normalized per generated electricity. In the same subplot, some data series show the increasing CC impacts at the same CF. However, the given scatter plots do not allow to identify further trends or to determine the most critical parameters.

Figure 18: Climate Change impacts plotted versus rated power, hub height, rotor diameter, long- and latitude, capacity factors and turbine age of onshore and offshore wind turbines in Great Britain.

The correlation between the technical parameters and the total CC impacts of the British wind turbine fleet is moderate to low (Figure A38). Similar to the Belgian fleet, the hub height shows the strongest correlation with the total CC impacts, followed by rotor diameter and rated power (0.31, 0.27, and 0.23). Similar trends are observed for the CC impacts of the component production and assembly stage. The transportation, maintenance and disposal stages show stronger correlations with rated power, hub height and rotor diameter and weaker correlations with the lifetime electricity production. Geographical data are found to have a low influence on the total CC impacts.

The regression model performance conducted for the British wind fleet is moderate ($R^2 = 0.385$). The model is statistically significant, as shown by the F-statistic of 782.3 ($p < 0.001$). Among the predictors, rated power, hub height, and lifetime electricity production show strong statistical significance ($p < 0.001$). The rated power and hub height have positive coefficients, suggesting they contribute positively to the total CC impact. Contrary, lifetime electricity production has a negative impact, with a very high t-value (-51.641). The rotor diameter is also significant ($p = 0.01$) but negatively associated with the CC impact. Longitude and Latitude are not statistically significant ($p = 0.549$ and $p = 0.951$, respectively), indicating they might not contribute meaningfully to the model (Figure A46).

The random forest model suggest lifetime electricity production as the most important feature, closely followed by hub height and rotor diameter. Other features, longitude, latitude and rated power reveal low importance (Figure A63).

Across all countries, lifetime electricity production consistently emerges as a critical parameter, showing a strong negative effect on total CC impacts. Hub height, rotor diameter, and rated power are also important, positively influencing total CC impacts. Geographical parameters such as longitude and latitude generally have limited influence, with the exception of regionalized parameters like sea depth and transportation distances, which indirectly affect component production stages. The random forest models largely align with these findings, emphasizing hub height, rotor diameter, and lifetime electricity production as the most relevant parameters for

minimizing climate change impacts. Figures for all analysis per country are provided in the ANNEX.

3.3.3 Impact on Biodiversity due to Land Use

Figure 19 shows the impact on biodiversity of the European wind turbine fleet in the ecoregions.

Figure 19: Impact on biodiversity of onshore European wind turbines. The limits of the ecoregion are shown on the map. Source of ecoregions limit: [28].

The initial land use type detected by BOKU in deliverable 1.4, before the European wind fleet is constructed, varies between countries (Figure 20). In most of them, wind turbines are built on agricultural surfaces, mainly non-irrigated arable land. Nonetheless, in Estonia, Greece, Ireland, Norway, Portugal and Sweden, wind turbines are mainly constructed on natural land. Notably, in Belgium, most of the onshore turbines are built on man-made land (industrial or commercial units, as well as ports) but this small country is the third country most artificialized in Europe [30].

Figure 20: Initial land use type before the construction of the European wind fleet, as detected by BOKU.

There is a large variability in the impact on biodiversity of direct LU of the European wind fleet: between 5.9E-3 PDF/turbine and 5.9 E-10 PDF/turbine, which is linked with the large variability in the land use change detected by BOKU in deliverable 1.4 (from 1.7 m²/turbine to 6.7E5 m²/turbine) (Figure 21). Both extremities in the values of change detection are questionable as 1m² per turbine cannot be true and more than 600,000m²/turbine seems to be due not only to turbine building but also to other changes in the landscape. However, the surface area does not explain alone all the variability of the impact on biodiversity. Some countries show a relatively larger impact per wind turbine: Norway, Ireland, United Kingdom and Estonia. As highlighted above, in Norway, Ireland and Estonia, the original LU is natural, which leads to higher impacts than if the turbines are built on agricultural land. On the other hand, Germany, and Luxembourg show a lower impact per wind turbine. In the annex, Figure A68 shows the distribution per country and Table A23 shows the mean, minimum, maximum, and quartiles for all the countries.

Figure 21: Impact on biodiversity of the direct land use of the European wind turbines. Each point represents a wind farm but values are shown per turbine.

The ecoregion is also a driver of this impact. As highlighted for Denmark and Italy, the difference between the impacts on wind turbines in different ecoregion can be several orders of magnitude (Figure 22 and Figure 23). Results for other countries can be found in the ANNEX, between Figure A69 and Figure A85. In ecoregions PA0412 (Central European mixed forests in Germany, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, Belarus, Ukraine, and Russia), PA0421 (English Lowlands beech forests in UK), PA0431 (Pannonian mixed forests in Hungary, Slovakia, Croatia, Slovenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Romania, Serbia, Austria, Czech Republic, and Ukraine), PA0432 (Po Basin mixed forests in Italy and Switzerland), PA1218 (South Appenine mixed montane forests in Italy) and PA1219 (Southeastern Iberian shrubs and woodlands in Spain), the average impact is one order of magnitude lower than the average of all countries analyzed. In PA1106 (Kola Peninsula tundra in Norway and Russia), PA0520 (Scandinavian coastal conifer forests) and PA1110 (Scandinavian Montane Birch forest and grasslands in Finland, Norway and Sweden), the average impacts are 2 orders of magnitude higher than the average of all countries analyzed (Figure 24).

Figure 22: Impact of the Danish wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. Each point represents a wind farm but values are shown per turbine. PA402= Atlantic mixed forests, and PA405= Baltic mixed forests.

Figure 23: Impact of the Italian wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. Each point represents a wind farm but values are shown per turbine. PA0401= Apennine deciduous montane forests, PA0432= Po Basin mixed forests, PA0501= Alps conifer and mixed forests, PA1211= Italian sclerophyllous and semi-deciduous forests, PA1218= South Apennine mixed montane forests and PA1222= Tyrrhenian-Adriatic Sclerophyllous and mixed forests.

Figure 24: Average impact per wind turbine of ecoregions. Source of ecoregions limit: [28].

3.4 Uncertainty evaluation

One important assumption assessed in this uncertainty evaluation is the lifetime of the turbines. In order to understand its influence, the default value of 20 years is modified to 18 years, representing lifetime of current wind turbines [1]. Contrary to the 18 years, a more optimistic lifetime of 30 years was investigated. First, the main leverage effect of the lifetime is for determining the lifetime electricity production, which is used to convert the absolute environmental impacts in their functional unit. Secondly, the lifetime is considered for transportation activities required for maintenance. Additionally, the lifetime is used to identify replacement of transformers. As

shown previously, those activities are found to have a minor influence on the total results. Unsurprisingly, longer lifetime results in lower environmental impacts whereas shorter lifetime ends up in higher environmental impacts (Figure A86 and Figure A87).

A second parameter modified is the connection to the electricity grid. By default, buses are chosen now as connection points for wind turbines with the power grid. Another grid entry point is chosen to understand the CC impacts and thus, power buses instead of transformers are chosen. As presented previously, the impact of cable length is found to have a lower effect on the total CC. Therefore, it is unsurprising that changing the grid entry point did not result in any visible change in total CC (Figure A88 and Figure A89).

Apart from those parameters affecting the foreground system, the sensitivity of the model towards the background data is assessed. Therefore, a Monte-Carlo simulation is conducted assuming a dependent sampling with 1,000 runs. Results of onshore wind turbines are summarized in Figure 25 and show that similar trends can be observed as when conducting a static LCA. Therefore, it can be concluded that the uncertainty coming from the background database is not very likely to change the overall output of the developed model.

Figure 25: Results of the Monte Carlo simulation with 1000 iterations for the five onshore case study wind turbines (GWP100 = Global warming potential with 100 year time frame).

3.5 Validation

LCA results cannot be validated with experimental results as LCA evaluates potential impacts. In order to validate an LCA model, it is common practice to compare results with literature and other models, to identify the differences between models and results, as well as their sources and implications.

The model presented here is compared to Sacchi et al. (2019). In their publication, they reported a median CC impact of 2MW onshore and offshore turbines for Denmark of 17.4 and 11.7 g CO₂eq/kWh [1]. Their results range from approximately 10 up to 30 g CO₂eq/kWh for the 2MW onshore and from 5 up to 20 g CO₂eq/kWh for the 2MW offshore turbines [1]. As in other studies, this section is not aiming at identifying why the presented results differ from previous studies, but rather to show that they fall within acceptable ranges.

With an average of 15.4 g CO₂eq/kWh reported by scientific literature, the presented results lie very well within, or even slightly below the range of existing studies. Exceptions are the average of the Norwegian offshore wind turbines and Belgium onshore wind turbines. Once outliers are removed, the

average CC of offshore and onshore wind turbines found in literature drops to 2.0 g CO₂eq/kWh and 9.7 g CO₂eq/kWh and corrected values are very well below results of this study: between 13 g CO₂eq/kWh for British onshore fleet and 17 g CO₂eq/kWh for Belgian onshore fleet, and between 12 g CO₂eq/kWh for British offshore fleet and 19 g CO₂eq/kWh fir Norwegian offshore fleet.

3.6 Discussion

In the previous sections, the strength of the developed model is demonstrated supported by statistical analysis to identify important input data and parameters. One point to highlight, concerns the case studies, which do not represent the average or default condition of the entire country. Instead, the results of the case study represent a very specific turbine setup at a given location and thus cannot be understood as a country representation of the entire wind fleet. A good example is the CF of offshore wind turbines that are selected as case studies. Those values originate from the interactive WIMBY map and are calculated using detailed model developed by DTU (deliverable 2.2). With CF varying from 46 up to 61%, those ranges exceed by 12–27% the average CF of the EU offshore wind fleet provided by Wind Europe [21]. As shown in the section 3.3.2, CF are found to be a major parameter when determining CC impacts of wind turbines at kWh-level. Thus, the presented results of the case studies have to be considered cautiously given those high CF.

The model and this work is subject to certain limitations. Following the previous point about the CF of the case studies, the calculation of the electricity production of the EU wind fleet is subject to simplifications. Instead of considering turbine-specific cut-in and cut-off speeds, affecting the determined power curves and thus the annual electricity production, the same cut-in and cut-off wind speeds for all the EU wind turbines are applied, as recommended by Saint-Drenan et al. (2020). Furthermore, the same parametric power curve model, based on rated power and rotor diameter, is used for all the EU wind fleet, neglecting for example turbulence kinetic energy. Ignoring turbine-specific conditions in the power curves such as cut-in and cut-off wind speeds or turbulence kinetic energy has a direct effect on the subsequently calculated electricity production and thus on the environmental impacts of the EU wind fleets. To decrease the uncertainty in the electricity production calculation, one way could have been to validate the determined power curves with a commercial database. This, however, would require a matching between the EU wind fleet turbines and the particular wind turbine model. As a consequence, the validation of the calculated power curves remains unaddressed. Instead, a validation step is done on the CF of the EU wind fleets. In this validation step, the CF of many

turbines are adjusted based on a set of rules, indicating that there is uncertainty introduced at some level of the electricity calculation of the EU wind fleet. As the main objective of this deliverable is to develop a regional LCA model for the calculation of on- and offshore turbines along with the delivery of spatially refined data and not to determine the electricity yield of the existing EU wind fleet, efforts are limited to this simplified approach, knowing that this is not a precise calculation with the objective to reflect real-world production.

Another limitation concerns input data, affecting all life cycle stages: over the last years, larger turbines entered the market with new generator technologies. Such new generator technologies do not only vary in material quantity, but also in material composition such as permanent magnets, being known for containing critical raw materials. The current model is in general capable of scaling up the turbine based on larger rated power, but does not take into account for example new generator technologies. To the authors knowledge, no study exists yet containing such detailed information as on material quantity per sub-component level, which is the required input data for the current LCA model. Therefore, the first claim is towards industry to be more transparent in their reporting, which would allow the scientific community to increase accuracy of their work and thus credibility of their results.

In a similar direction goes the need for more data regarding end-of-life (EoL) treatment. When analyzing the ecosystem of EoL treatment of wind turbines, included in the first version of this deliverable, it becomes very quickly evident that all efforts on treatment of current retired wind turbines are, if at all, at lab scale. Thus, reliable data to model a future EoL are not available. Including any other EoL treatment would have been very hypothetical, as currently nobody knows how future treatment on a large scale of retired wind turbines would look like and thus increased drastically uncertainty. With the current European wind turbine fleet getting older, it should be up to policy makers to start thinking about a legal framework for those huge upcoming waste streams. Researchers can support this process by starting to model and assess those waste streams, for example using a material-flow analysis combined with life cycle assessment. However, this task is out of WIMBY's scope and will remain open for future research. A very nice example on individual turbine level is the paper of Diez-Cañamero and

Mendoza (2023), where they analyze the circular economy performance and carbon footprint of wind turbine blades [31].

Next, some simplifications are made when modelling the regional LCI: first, for both transportation distances and cable lengths, the direct distance is considered between the manufacturing and turbine location for transportation and the buses and the turbine location for cable lengths. Obviously, this does not depict reality, e.g. as for transportation, the trucks would travel on the road and use existing infrastructure. Similarly, the cable will not necessarily be able to cross all different areas, e.g. lakes, high mountains, buildings, etc. Nevertheless, this input data is used in the LCA model as the contribution towards the final results remain so little, that changing those input data would affect total environmental impacts only marginally. Until then, this model can be used as a valid proxy.

Still, the analysis of the wind turbines in all case studies pointed out the CF as main driver for the environmental impacts. For the European wind fleet evaluation, this poses a limitation as underlying power curves are theoretical models, but this way regional conditions could be integrated into LCA and spatially differentiated results can be built. At the same time, the map integration of the LCA model will overcome this as the CF and the annual electricity yield originates from detailed models and are consequently used to normalize total environmental impacts, the LCA results benefit from the reliability of those models.

The assessment of the impact of wind turbines on the biodiversity is here focusing on LU, which is at a global level the main driver of biodiversity loss. However, human-induced mortality of large migratory birds due to energy infrastructure are first caused by electrocution, power line collision, and wind-farm collision[32]: 48.98 % among which 40.5 % are due to electrocution. The exclusion of electrocution and power line collision is a limitation of this study but was out of the scope of this task. Also, the impact of sea use on biodiversity, for offshore turbines, is not included, due to the lack of potential assessment based on satellite data, in WPI. In deliverable 1.4, offshore wind farm impacts are evaluated using empirical data and literature due to satellite imagery limitations. Also, the lack of ChF for seabed use prevents to have the same assessment and obtain results in terms of PDF.

The last two points are rather an open call for both manufacturer and operator. As the analysis showed, the environmental impacts decrease with longer lifetimes. This can be already considered in the design phase, e.g. the planned obsolescence needs to be extended as long as possible making turbines ready for operation as long as possible. Of course, guaranteeing the long liability is not purely the responsibility of the manufacturer, but also requires regular maintenance efforts from the operator.

Finally, this research is still limited in terms of its full evaluation, partly because more recent and detailed data is currently hold back from industry. However, in order to overcome the climate crisis and work towards enabling the energy transition, we should join forces as good as we can and stop restricting each other by holding back crucial information.

Regardless of the limitations, the developed LCA model is capable of capturing and calculating environmental impacts of a wind turbine that is installed at a given location, taking into account its geographic position. This in combination with a code that minimizes the computational requirements makes the model suitable for integration into the WIMBY interactive map, which is is a crucial criteria within the WIMBY project.

CONCLUSIONS

Within this deliverable, an LCA model to calculate environmental impacts of onshore and offshore wind turbines considering regional conditions is presented. An existing LCA model is enhanced by determining connection cable length to the electricity grid, calculating transportation distances between various component manufacturing locations and the turbines installation side, considering different foundation types given varying sea depth and using country-specific dataset during installation, operation and end-of-life treatment. The model uses a functional unit of one kilowatt electricity produced by the wind turbine. On- and offshore Turbines installed in five countries, namely France, Italy, Norway, Belgium and Germany are selected to demonstrate the model's outcome. Afterwards, the climate change impact of the country fleet is calculated and a statistical analysis is performed with the object to understand the models' interrelationships and the most important parameters. In a second step, a geographically differentiated life cycle impact assessment method is developed. Therefore, data on surface change are obtained from another WIMBY task and matched with Ecoregions. The development is then demonstrated and visualized for the entire European wind fleet.

In general, there is a great variety of the climate change impacts of the analyzed wind turbines. One observation is that the parts improved with regionalized life cycle inventory data do not have a large impact on the total climate change compared to other life cycle stage activities and processes. Nevertheless, it is observed that there is still a variance when assessing different locations. A second observation is the importance of the lifetime electricity production, which is identified by the correlation, regression and random forest analysis as the most important parameter. This can be explained mainly by the selection of the functional unit. Lower importance is given to the location parameters of the wind turbines, being in agreement with the observation on a turbine level.

The main drivers of the impact of wind turbine land use on biodiversity are: the surface area change, the original land use type before the wind turbine is built and the ecoregion. The bigger the direct change surface area, the higher the impact on biodiversity. Building wind turbines on natural land and

not on agricultural land should not be recommended considering the larger impact it has.

After pointing out its limitation, the main contribution of the developed model is the computational speed per turbine, which is one important criteria for a seamless integration into the WIMBY interactive map and thus a success for the WIMBY project.

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ANNEX

1. Modifiedecoinvent datasets

```
# Function to determine locations based on the 'Phase' column
def determine_location(row, iso_code):
    if row['Phase'] == 'Input':
        return ['GLO', 'RoW', 'RER', 'Europe without Switzerland', 'CH']
    elif row['Phase'] == 'Assembly':
        return [iso_code, 'RER', 'Europe without Switzerland', 'GLO', 'RoW']
    elif row['Phase'] == 'Maintenance':
        return [iso_code, 'RER', 'Europe without Switzerland']
    elif row['Phase'] == 'Disposal':
        return [iso_code, 'RER', 'Europe without Switzerland', 'RoW']
    else:
        return []
```

Figure A26: Dictionary to modify the location of ecoinvent datasets depending on the life cycle stage and the country where the wind turbine is installed (GLO = global, RoW = rest of the world, RER = rest of Europe).

Power	Phase	Component	Sub-component	Dataset	Unit	Quantity	Database name	Market name	UUID	Location	
6	30kW	Assembly	Nacelle	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	kWh	575.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO
21	30kW	Disposal	Power supply	Cable	PP granules	kg	20.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for waste polypropylene	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, 758cdb70c326950e77c3a1f403d855c8)	NO
87	150kW	Assembly	Nacelle	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	kWh	3987.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO
117	150kW	Disposal	Power supply	Cable	PP granules	kg	20.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for waste polypropylene	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, 758cdb70c326950e77c3a1f403d855c8)	NO
155	600kW	Assembly	Nacelle	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	kWh	17510.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO
168	600kW	Assembly	Foundation	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	kWh	5.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO
183	600kW	Disposal	Power supply	Cable	PP granules	kg	20.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for waste polypropylene	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, 758cdb70c326950e77c3a1f403d855c8)	NO
221	800kW	Assembly	Nacelle	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	kWh	17510.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO
234	800kW	Assembly	Foundation	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	kWh	10.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO
249	800kW	Disposal	Power supply	Cable	PP granules	kg	20.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for waste polypropylene	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, 758cdb70c326950e77c3a1f403d855c8)	NO
287	2000kW	Assembly	Nacelle	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	kWh	67500.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO

Figure A27: Overview of ecoinvent datasets including life cycle stages which are selected based on the identified ISO code for onshore wind turbines.

Power	Phase	Component	Sub-component	Dataset	Unit	Quantity	Database name	Market name	UUID	Location
6	30kW	Assembly	Nacelle	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	575.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO
21	30kW	Disposal	Power supply	Cable	PP granules	kg	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for waste polypropylene	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, 758cdb70c326950e77c3a1f403d855c8)	NO
87	150kW	Assembly	Nacelle	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	3987.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO
117	150kW	Disposal	Power supply	Cable	PP granules	kg	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for waste polypropylene	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, 758cdb70c326950e77c3a1f403d855c8)	NO
155	600kW	Assembly	Nacelle	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	17510.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO
168	600kW	Assembly	Foundation	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	5.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO
183	600kW	Disposal	Power supply	Cable	PP granules	kg	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for waste polypropylene	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, 758cdb70c326950e77c3a1f403d855c8)	NO
221	800kW	Assembly	Nacelle	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	17510.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO
234	800kW	Assembly	Foundation	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	10.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO
249	800kW	Disposal	Power supply	Cable	PP granules	kg	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for waste polypropylene	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, 758cdb70c326950e77c3a1f403d855c8)	NO
287	2000kW	Assembly	Nacelle	Assembly	Electricity [kWh]	67500.0	ecoinvent cutoff 391	market for electricity, high voltage	(ecoinvent-391-cutoff, c880ee65ad6eb9c614323bb9b1a08a3f)	NO

Figure A28: Overview of ecoinvent datasets including life cycle stages which are selected based on the identified ISO code for offshore wind turbines.

2. Climate change impacts

2.1 France

2.2 Italy

2.3 Norway

2.4 Germany

2.5 Belgium

3. Correlation between surface change area (convexhull) and turbine parameters

Country	Hub height	Rated power	Diameter
Austria	0.023947	-0.416032	-0.436651
Belgium	0.185506	0.201668	0.114090
Estonia	NaN	NaN	NaN
France	-0.007286	0.181339	0.066685
Germany	0.086799	0.061060	0.057979
Greece	NaN	NaN	NaN
Ireland	0.833885	0.097584	0.465737
Italy	-0.428907	-0.250079	-0.679766
Latvia	NaN	NaN	NaN
Lithuania	NaN	NaN	NaN
Luxembourg	NaN	NaN	NaN
Netherlands	-0.465383	-0.328835	-0.462253
Norway	-0.003920	-0.149206	0.099505
Portugal	-1.0	-1.0	-1.0
Spain	-0.367819	-0.763477	-0.107487
Sweden	0.111908	0.036203	0.110614
UK	0.275397	0.315575	0.457491
All countries together	-0.048164	0.066468	0.032161

4. Co-occurrence matrix for the case study ecoregions

Corinne Land use type	PA0402	PA0445	PA0520	PA1222
Continuous urban fabric	Urban intense	Urban light		Urban light
Discontinuous urban fabric	Cropland intense	Cropland intense		
Industrial or commercial units	Cropland intense	Cropland intense	Cropland intense	Cropland intense
Road and rail networks and associated land	Cropland intense	Cropland intense	Managed forests light	Urban light
Port areas	Urban intense	Urban light	Primary and secondary vegetation	
Airports	Cropland intense	Cropland intense		Cropland intense

Mineral extraction sites	Cropland intense	Cropland intense	Primary and secondary vegetation	Primary and secondary vegetation
Dump sites	Cropland intense	Cropland intense	Urban light	Cropland intense
Construction sites	Cropland intense	Cropland intense	Managed forests light	Cropland light
Green urban areas	Urban intense	Urban light		Urban intense
Sport and leisure facilities	Cropland intense	Cropland intense	Primary and secondary vegetation	
Non-irrigated arable land	Cropland intense	Cropland intense	Cropland intense	Cropland light
Permanently irrigated land				Cropland intense
Rice fields				Cropland intense
Vineyards	Primary and secondary vegetation	Cropland intense		Cropland intense
Fruit trees and berry plantations	Cropland intense	Cropland intense		Cropland intense
Olive groves				Primary and secondary vegetation
Pastures	Cropland intense	Cropland intense	Cropland intense	Cropland light
Annual crops associated with permanent crops				Cropland light
Complex cultivation patterns	Cropland intense	Pasture minimal	Primary and secondary vegetation	Primary and secondary vegetation
Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation	Cropland intense	Cropland intense	Primary and secondary vegetation	Primary and secondary vegetation
Agro-forestry areas			Primary and secondary vegetation	Pasture light

Broad-leaved forest	Cropland intense	Managed forests light	Primary and secondary vegetation	Managed forests minimal
Coniferous forest	Primary and secondary vegetation	Primary and secondary vegetation	Primary and secondary vegetation	Managed forests minimal
Mixed forest	Cropland intense	Primary and secondary vegetation	Primary and secondary vegetation	Primary and secondary vegetation
Natural grasslands		Pasture minimal		Managed forests minimal
Moors and heathland	Primary and secondary vegetation	Managed forests minimal	Primary and secondary vegetation	Managed forests minimal
Sclerophyllous vegetation	Managed forests light	Managed forests minimal		Managed forests minimal
Transitional woodland-shrub	Primary and secondary vegetation	Primary and secondary vegetation	Managed forests light	Primary and secondary vegetation
Beaches, dunes, sands		Cropland intense		Primary and secondary vegetation
Bare rocks		Managed forests minimal	Primary and secondary vegetation	Managed forests minimal
Sparsely vegetated areas		Managed forests minimal	Primary and secondary vegetation	Managed forests minimal
Burnt areas	Primary and secondary vegetation			Managed forests minimal
Glaciers and perpetual snow			Primary and secondary vegetation	

Inland marshes	Cropland intense	Primary and secondary vegetation		Primary and secondary vegetation
Peat bogs	Cropland intense	Primary and secondary vegetation	Primary and secondary vegetation	

5. Remaining results and charts

Figure A29: Validation of lifetime electricity production for European offshore turbines. The orange bars represent a theoretical calculation considering the rated power, the average CF for offshore wind turbines in 2022 and a minimum and maximum lifetime of 20 and 30 years. The blue dots represent data considering average wind speed data and retrieved power curves.

Figure A30: Validation of lifetime electricity production for European onshore turbines. The orange bars represent a theoretical calculation considering the rated power, the average CF for offshore wind turbines in 2022 and a minimum and maximum lifetime of 20 and 30 years. The blue dots represent data considering average wind speed data and retrieved power curves.

Offshore fleet GB					
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Disposal	Total
Count	2,245	2,245	2,245	2,245	2,245
Mean	0.011613	0.001801	0.001474	-0.00037	0.014851
Std	0.005509	0.001060	0.000358	-0.000016	0.006810
Min	0.006324	0.000807	0.000728	-0.000108	0.008104
25%	0.008688	0.001285	0.001205	-0.000048	0.011291
50%	0.010137	0.001476	0.001456	-0.000030	0.013186
75%	0.011095	0.001669	0.001739	-0.000026	0.014286
Max	0.026825	0.004657	0.002338	-0.000019	0.032967

Table A7: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the offshore wind turbine fleet in Great Britain, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Offshore fleet BE					
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Disposal	Total
Count	401	401	401	401	401
Mean	0.012698	0.001917	0.001310	-0.000022	0.015904
Std	0.006552	0.001210	0.000290	0.000005	0.007926
Min	0.007015	0.000905	0.000886	-0.000030	0.008781
25%	0.007466	0.001005	0.001067	-0.000026	0.009555
50%	0.010454	0.001352	0.001225	-0.000023	0.013287
75%	0.015884	0.002640	0.001506	-0.000016	0.019701
Max	0.026119	0.004381	0.001882	-0.000014	0.031865

Table A8: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the offshore wind turbine fleet in Belgium, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Offshore fleet NO					
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Disposal	Total
Count	3	3	3	3	3
Mean	0.019323	0.002772	0.001638	-0.000051	0.023682
Std	0.006273	0.001303	0.000443	0.000023	0.007773
Min	0.012222	0.001285	0.001250	-0.000077	0.014972
25%	0.016931	0.002301	0.001396	-0.000062	0.020566
50%	0.021640	0.003317	0.001541	-0.000047	0.026161
75%	0.022874	0.003516	0.001831	-0.000038	0.028037
Max	0.024107	0.003715	0.002121	-0.000030	0.029913

Table A9: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the offshore wind turbine fleet in Norway, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Offshore fleet IT					
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Disposal	Total
Count	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
Std	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
Min	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
25%	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
50%	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
75%	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
Max	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

Table A10: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the offshore wind turbine fleet in Italy, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Offshore fleet AT					
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Disposal	Total
Count	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
Std	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
Min	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
25%	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
50%	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
75%	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
Max	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

Table A11: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the offshore wind turbine fleet in Austria, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Offshore fleet DK					
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Disposal	Total
Count	604	604	604	604	604
Mean	0.009506	0.001316	0.001269	-0.000047	0.012043
Std	0.001247	0.000267	0.000263	0.000024	0.001737
Min	0.007151	0.000928	0.000708	-0.000166	0.008930
25%	0.008657	0.001144	0.001074	-0.000060	0.010849
50%	0.010093	0.001312	0.001214	-0.000042	0.012501
75%	0.010584	0.001420	0.001536	-0.000027	0.013509
Max	0.010875	0.001946	0.001644	-0.000020	0.014397

Table A12: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the offshore wind turbine fleet in Denmark, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Offshore fleet FR					
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Disposal	Total
Count	2	2	2	2	2
Mean	0.026428	0.004314	0.001404	-0.000034	0.032113
Std	0.008141	0.001502	0.000368	0.000019	0.009257
Min	0.020672	0.003252	0.001144	-0.000047	0.025567
25%	0.023550	0.003783	0.001274	-0.000041	0.028840
50%	0.026428	0.004314	0.001404	-0.000034	0.032113
75%	0.029307	0.004845	0.001534	-0.000028	0.035385
Max	0.032185	0.005377	0.001664	-0.000021	0.038658

Table A13: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the offshore wind turbine fleet in France, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Offshore fleet PT					
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Disposal	Total
Count	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
Std	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
Min	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
25%	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
50%	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
75%	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
Max	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

Table A14: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the offshore wind turbine fleet in Portugal, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Onshore fleet GB						
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Maintenance	Disposal	Total
Count	5,248	5,248	5,248	5,248	5,248	5,248
Mean	0.013308	0.001865	0.001314	0.000005	-0.000098	0.016395
Std	0.003350	0.000477	0.000444	0.000003	0.000062	0.004231
Min	0.006392	0.000889	0.000501	0.000000	-0.000758	0.007863
25%	0.010858	0.001521	0.000983	0.000003	-0.000116	0.013205
50%	0.012677	0.001774	0.001231	0.000004	-0.000080	0.015516
75%	0.015010	0.002078	0.001593	0.000006	-0.000058	0.018556
Max	0.030269	0.005050	0.003566	0.000028	-0.000022	0.038752

Table A15: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the onshore wind turbine fleet in Great Britain, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Onshore fleet BE						
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Maintenance	Disposal	Total
Count	816	816	816	816	816	816
Mean	0.016620	0.002296	0.002046	0.000004	-0.000078	0.020888
Std	0.003328	0.000482	0.000475	0.000002	0.000032	0.004238
Min	0.007393	0.001044	0.000717	0.000000	-0.000184	0.009089
25%	0.015075	0.002047	0.001795	0.000003	-0.000098	0.018892
50%	0.016652	0.002280	0.002084	0.000004	-0.000072	0.020969
75%	0.018629	0.002569	0.002319	0.000005	-0.000053	0.023594
Max	0.025056	0.003910	0.003508	0.000022	-0.000024	0.032088

Table A16: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the onshore wind turbine fleet in Belgium, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Onshore fleet NO						
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Maintenance	Disposal	Total
Count	853	853	853	853	853	853
Mean	0.014820	0.001587	0.001828	0.000003	-0.000113	0.018124
Std	0.004516	0.000731	0.000740	0.000001	0.000107	0.005904
Min	0.006802	0.000759	0.000595	0.000000	-0.000412	0.008072
25%	0.012143	0.001226	0.001263	0.000002	-0.000142	0.014617
50%	0.013705	0.001426	0.001657	0.000002	-0.000061	0.16358
75%	0.016330	0.001872	0.002138	0.000003	-0.000043	0.020035
Max	0.033713	0.006106	0.004908	0.000014	-0.000019	0.044573

Table A17: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the onshore wind turbine fleet in Norway, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Onshore fleet IT						
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Maintenance	Disposal	Total
Count	4,122	4,122	4,122	4,122	4,122	4,122
Mean	0.012856	0.001879	0.001873	0.000006	-0.000099	0.016315
Std	0.002226	0.000361	0.000443	0.000003	0.000036	0.003022
Min	0.009788	0.001467	0.000976	0.000000	-0.000234	0.012329
25%	0.011222	0.001718	0.001247	0.000004	-0.000118	0.014136
50%	0.011984	0.001855	0.001384	0.000004	-0.000094	0.014972
75%	0.014563	0.002216	0.001904	0.000010	-0.000074	0.018623
Max	0.023127	0.003811	0.004389	0.000014	-0.000032	0.030276

Table A18: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the onshore wind turbine fleet in Italy, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Onshore fleet AT						
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Maintenance	Disposal	Total
Count	952	952	952	952	952	952
Mean	0.015244	0.002178	0.001954	0.000004	-0.000077	0.019303
Std	0.004227	0.000645	0.000780	0.000001	0.0000.0	0.005633
Min	0.009884	0.001263	0.000854	0.000001	-0.000260	0.011864
25%	0.011668	0.001697	0.001295	0.000003	-0.000091	0.14582
50%	0.014711	0.002156	0.001810	0.000004	-0.000071	0.018573
75%	0.017058	0.002410	0.002395	0.000004	-0.000056	0.021758
Max	0.037254	0.005484	0.005784	0.000015	-0.000030	0.048372

Table A19: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the onshore wind turbine fleet in Austria, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Onshore fleet DK						
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Maintenance	Disposal	Total
Count	4,328	4,328	4,328	4,328	4,328	4,328
Mean	0.024240	0.004033	0.002738	0.000033	-0.000168	0.030875
Std	0.027875	0.005294	0.003892	0.000059	0.000206	0.037010
Min	0.005896	0.000833	0.000408	0.000000	-0.011735	0.007120
25%	0.010364	0.001419	0.000778	0.000003	-0.000227	0.012482
50%	0.011807	0.001694	0.000937	0.000006	-0.000125	0.014282
75%	0.015935	0.002134	0.001597	0.000011	-0.000088	0.019504
Max	0.165584	0.024136	0.012995	0.000170	-0.000020	0.190980

Table A20: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the onshore wind turbine fleet in Denmark, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Onshore fleet FR						
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Maintenance	Disposal	Total
Count	6,259	6,259	6,259	6,259	6,259	6,259
Mean	0.017372	0.00205	0.002097	0.000005	-0.000095	0.021434
Std	0.005235	0.000623	0.000797	0.000002	0.000036	0.006612
Min	0.005999	0.000650	0.000530	0.000000	-0.000249	0.007276
25%	0.013115	0.001580	0.001467	0.000005	-0.000115	0.016024
50%	0.016418	0.001944	0.002026	0.000004	-0.000090	0.020239
75%	0.021081	0.002497	0.002604	0.000006	-0.000069	0.026136
Max	0.34764	0.004227	0.005040	0.000018	-0.000029	0.043738

Table A21: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the onshore wind turbine fleet in France, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Onshore fleet PT						
	Component production	Assembly	Transport	Maintenance	Disposal	Total
Count	1,675	1,675	1,675	1,675	1,675	1,675
Mean	0.013071	0.001906	0.001470	0.000004	-0.000082	0.016369
Std	0.002546	0.000382	0.000379	0.000001	0.000030	0.003281
Min	0.009090	0.001281	0.000888	0.000002	-0.000193	0.011499
25%	0.011365	0.001649	0.001182	0.000004	-0.000097	0.014198
50%	0.013087	0.001868	0.001463	0.000004	-0.000079	0.016338
75%	0.013924	0.002046	0.001601	0.000004	-0.000062	0.017472
Max	0.022135	0.003532	0.002841	0.000011	-0.000031	0.028010

Table A22: Describing statistics of the Climate Change impact of the onshore wind turbine fleet in Portugal, where count represents number of turbines and other values climate change impact in kg CO₂eq/kWh generated electricity.

Figure A31: Histogram of Climate Change impacts of on- and offshore wind turbines in Great Britain.

Figure A32: Histogram of Climate Change Impacts of on- and offshore wind turbines in Norway.

Figure A33: Histogram of Climate Change Impacts of onshore wind turbines in Italy.

Figure A34: Histogram of Climate Change Impacts of onshore wind turbines in Austria.

Figure A35: Histogram of Climate Change Impacts of on- and offshore wind turbines in Denmark.

Figure A36: Histogram of Climate Change Impacts of on- and offshore wind turbines in France.

Figure A37: Histogram of Climate Change Impacts of onshore wind turbines in Portugal.

Figure A38: Correlation between Climate Change impacts (here represented in the columns/rows Component production, Assembly, Transport, Maintenance, Disposal and Total) for onshore wind turbines in Great Britain.

Figure A39: Correlation between Climate Change impacts (here represented in the columns/rows Component production, Assembly, Transport, Maintenance, Disposal and Total) for onshore wind turbines in Belgium.

Figure A40: Correlation between Climate Change impacts (here represented in the columns/rows Component production, Assembly, Transport, Maintenance, Disposal and Total) for onshore wind turbines in Norway.

Figure A41: Correlation between Climate Change impacts (here represented in the columns/rows Component production, Assembly, Transport, Maintenance, Disposal and Total) for onshore wind turbines in Italy.

Figure A42: Correlation between Climate Change impacts (here represented in the columns/rows Component production, Assembly, Transport, Maintenance, Disposal and Total) for onshore wind turbines in Austria.

Figure A43: Correlation between Climate Change impacts (here represented in the columns/rows Component production, Assembly, Transport, Maintenance, Disposal and Total) for onshore wind turbines in France.

Figure A44: Correlation between Climate Change impacts (here represented in the columns/rows Component production, Assembly, Transport, Maintenance, Disposal and Total) for onshore wind turbines in Denmark.

Figure A45: Correlation between Climate Change impacts (here represented in the columns/rows Component production, Assembly, Transport, Maintenance, Disposal and Total) for onshore wind turbines in Portugal.


```

OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          Total    R-squared:              0.385
Model:                 OLS      Adj. R-squared:         0.385
Method:                Least Squares    F-statistic:            782.3
Date:                  Wed, 19 Feb 2025    Prob (F-statistic):      0.00
Time:                  08:34:17    Log-Likelihood:          30614.
No. Observations:      7493    AIC:                    -6.121e+04
Df Residuals:          7486    BIC:                    -6.116e+04
Df Model:              6
Covariance Type:      nonrobust
=====
                    coef    std err          t      P>|t|      [0.025    0.975]
-----
const                0.0074      0.001      4.953    0.000      0.004    0.010
P_rated_kw          5.382e-06      1.5e-07    35.953    0.000    5.09e-06    5.67e-06
Hub_height_m        0.0001      5.22e-06    19.177    0.000    8.99e-05    0.000
Diameter_m         -1.572e-05      6.09e-06    -2.581    0.010    -2.77e-05    -3.78e-06
Longitude           1.535e-05      2.56e-05     0.599    0.549    -3.49e-05    6.56e-05
Latitude            -1.678e-06      2.75e-05    -0.061    0.951    -5.55e-05    5.22e-05
Lifetime_production_kWh -8.433e-11      1.63e-12   -51.641    0.000    -8.75e-11    -8.11e-11
=====
Omnibus:              2277.885    Durbin-Watson:          0.442
Prob(Omnibus):        0.000    Jarque-Bera (JB):       6260.064
Skew:                 1.627    Prob(JB):                0.00
...
Notes:
[1] Standard Errors assume that the covariance matrix of the errors is correctly specified.
[2] The condition number is large, 5.74e+09. This might indicate that there are
strong multicollinearity or other numerical problems.

```

Figure A46: Summary of regression results of the wind turbine fleet of Great Britain.

```

OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          Total    R-squared:              0.434
Model:                 OLS      Adj. R-squared:         0.431
Method:                Least Squares    F-statistic:            154.5
Date:                  Wed, 19 Feb 2025    Prob (F-statistic):     1.25e-145
Time:                  08:34:42    Log-Likelihood:          4809.9
No. Observations:      1217    AIC:                    -9606.
Df Residuals:          1210    BIC:                    -9570.
Df Model:              6
Covariance Type:      nonrobust
=====
                    coef    std err          t      P>|t|      [0.025    0.975]
-----
const               -0.0808      0.021     -3.938    0.000     -0.121    -0.041
P_rated_kw          2.438e-06      2.98e-07     8.186    0.000    1.85e-06    3.02e-06
Hub_height_m        9.805e-05      1.15e-05     8.494    0.000    7.54e-05    0.000
Diameter_m          9.489e-05      1.32e-05     7.178    0.000    6.9e-05    0.000
Longitude           0.0008      0.000      3.667    0.000    0.000    0.001
Latitude            0.0015      0.000      3.934    0.000    0.001    0.002
Lifetime_production_kWh -5.06e-11      2.68e-12   -18.849    0.000    -5.59e-11    -4.53e-11
=====
Omnibus:              195.248    Durbin-Watson:          0.598
Prob(Omnibus):        0.000    Jarque-Bera (JB):       328.908
Skew:                 1.027    Prob(JB):                3.79e-72
...
Notes:
[1] Standard Errors assume that the covariance matrix of the errors is correctly specified.
[2] The condition number is large, 4.24e+10. This might indicate that there are
strong multicollinearity or other numerical problems.

```

Figure A47: Summary of regression results of the wind turbine fleet of Belgium.


```

=====
                        OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          Total      R-squared:              0.901
Model:                 OLS      Adj. R-squared:         0.900
Method:                Least Squares  F-statistic:           1281.
Date:                  Wed, 19 Feb 2025  Prob (F-statistic):     0.00
Time:                  08:35:08    Log-Likelihood:        4165.3
No. Observations:     856        AIC:                   -8317.
Df Residuals:         849        BIC:                   -8283.
Df Model:              6
Covariance Type:      nonrobust
=====
                        coef      std err      t      P>|t|      [0.025      0.975]
-----
const                  0.0042      0.003      1.296      0.195      -0.002      0.010
P_rated_kw            1.521e-06    3.3e-07    4.614      0.000      8.74e-07    2.17e-06
Hub_height_m         0.0002      6.46e-06    25.192     0.000      0.000      0.000
Diameter_m           0.0002      1.2e-05    15.035     0.000      0.000      0.000
Longitude             6.052e-05    3.45e-05    1.756      0.079     -7.11e-06    0.000
Latitude             -0.0001      5.19e-05    -2.504     0.012     -0.000     -2.81e-05
Lifetime_production_kwh -1.216e-10    2.37e-12   -51.261     0.000     -1.26e-10   -1.17e-10
=====
Omnibus:              754.200    Durbin-Watson:         0.493
Prob(Omnibus):        0.000     Jarque-Bera (JB):      28610.811
Skew:                 3.854     Prob(JB):              0.00
...
Notes:
[1] Standard Errors assume that the covariance matrix of the errors is correctly specified.
[2] The condition number is large, 7.83e+09. This might indicate that there are
strong multicollinearity or other numerical problems.

```

Figure A48: Summary of regression results of the wind turbine fleet of Norway.

```

=====
                        OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          Total      R-squared:              0.923
Model:                 OLS      Adj. R-squared:         0.923
Method:                Least Squares  F-statistic:           8246.
Date:                  Wed, 19 Feb 2025  Prob (F-statistic):     0.00
Time:                  08:35:21    Log-Likelihood:        23357.
No. Observations:     4122       AIC:                   -4.670e+04
Df Residuals:         4115       BIC:                   -4.666e+04
Df Model:              6
Covariance Type:      nonrobust
=====
                        coef      std err      t      P>|t|      [0.025      0.975]
-----
const                  0.0010      0.000      2.821      0.005      0.000      0.002
P_rated_kw            6.074e-06    2e-07     30.377     0.000     5.68e-06    6.47e-06
Hub_height_m         9.357e-05    2.68e-06    34.902     0.000     8.83e-05    9.88e-05
Diameter_m           0.0002      2.11e-06    104.168     0.000      0.000      0.000
Longitude             5.035e-05    5.84e-06    8.620      0.000     3.89e-05    6.18e-05
Latitude             1.798e-05    7.93e-06    2.268      0.023     2.44e-06    3.35e-05
Lifetime_production_kwh -2.668e-10    4.66e-12   -57.284     0.000     -2.76e-10   -2.58e-10
=====
Omnibus:              5809.006    Durbin-Watson:         0.787
Prob(Omnibus):        0.000     Jarque-Bera (JB):      4437345.068
Skew:                 7.813     Prob(JB):              0.00
...
Notes:
[1] Standard Errors assume that the covariance matrix of the errors is correctly specified.
[2] The condition number is large, 1.83e+09. This might indicate that there are
strong multicollinearity or other numerical problems.

```

Figure A49: Summary of regression results of the wind turbine fleet of Italy.


```

OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          Total    R-squared:              0.919
Model:                 OLS      Adj. R-squared:         0.918
Method:               Least Squares  F-statistic:           1782.
Date:                 Wed, 19 Feb 2025  Prob (F-statistic):     0.00
Time:                 08:35:32    Log-Likelihood:        4775.2
No. Observations:     952        AIC:                   -9536.
Df Residuals:         945        BIC:                   -9502.
Df Model:              6
Covariance Type:      nonrobust
=====
                    coef    std err          t      P>|t|      [0.025    0.975]
-----
const                0.0011    0.008         0.142    0.887    -0.014    0.016
P_rated_kw           1.045e-05  4.09e-07    25.520    0.000    9.64e-06  1.13e-05
Hub_height_m         8.497e-05  4.41e-06    19.259    0.000    7.63e-05  9.36e-05
Diameter_m           0.0003    7.74e-06    34.478    0.000    0.000    0.000
Longitude            -0.0006    7.99e-05   -7.308    0.000    -0.001    -0.000
Latitude             0.0002    0.000        1.142    0.254    -0.000    0.000
Lifetime_production_kwh -3.831e-10  7.95e-12   -48.205    0.000   -3.99e-10 -3.67e-10
=====
Omnibus:              901.457    Durbin-Watson:         1.201
Prob(Omnibus):        0.000     Jarque-Bera (JB):     37404.433
Skew:                 4.339     Prob(JB):              0.00
...
Notes:
[1] Standard Errors assume that the covariance matrix of the errors is correctly specified.
[2] The condition number is large, 1.45e+10. This might indicate that there are
strong multicollinearity or other numerical problems.

```

Figure A50: Summary of regression results of the wind turbine fleet of Austria.

```

OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          Total    R-squared:              0.517
Model:                 OLS      Adj. R-squared:         0.516
Method:               Least Squares  F-statistic:           878.7
Date:                 Wed, 19 Feb 2025  Prob (F-statistic):     0.00
Time:                 08:35:42    Log-Likelihood:        11300.
No. Observations:     4932       AIC:                   -2.259e+04
Df Residuals:         4925       BIC:                   -2.254e+04
Df Model:              6
Covariance Type:      nonrobust
=====
                    coef    std err          t      P>|t|      [0.025    0.975]
-----
const                -0.1706    0.027        -6.210    0.000    -0.224    -0.117
P_rated_kw           3.472e-05  1.4e-06    24.763    0.000    3.2e-05  3.75e-05
Hub_height_m        -0.0018    7.4e-05   -24.230    0.000    -0.002    -0.002
Diameter_m          -0.0003    6.71e-05   -4.450    0.000    -0.000    -0.000
Longitude            -0.0011    0.000       -3.721    0.000    -0.002    -0.001
Latitude             0.0051    0.000     10.928    0.000    0.004    0.006
Lifetime_production_kwh -2.297e-10  1.98e-11   -11.592    0.000   -2.69e-10 -1.91e-10
=====
Omnibus:              390.056    Durbin-Watson:         0.465
Prob(Omnibus):        0.000     Jarque-Bera (JB):     430.281
Skew:                 0.689     Prob(JB):              3.68e-94
...
Notes:
[1] Standard Errors assume that the covariance matrix of the errors is correctly specified.
[2] The condition number is large, 8.85e+09. This might indicate that there are
strong multicollinearity or other numerical problems.

```

Figure A51: Summary of regression results of the wind turbine fleet of Denmark.


```

=====
                        OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          Total      R-squared:                0.910
Model:                  OLS      Adj. R-squared:           0.910
Method:                 Least Squares  F-statistic:              1.054e+04
Date:                   Wed, 19 Feb 2025  Prob (F-statistic):       0.00
Time:                   08:35:51   Log-Likelihood:           30074.
No. Observations:      6261      AIC:                      -6.013e+04
Df Residuals:          6254      BIC:                      -6.009e+04
Df Model:               6
Covariance Type:       nonrobust
=====
                        coef      std err      t      P>|t|      [0.025      0.975]
-----
const                   0.0033      0.001      5.395      0.000      0.002      0.005
P_rated_kw              3.342e-06   9.03e-08   37.033     0.000     3.17e-06   3.52e-06
Hub_height_m            0.0001     2.38e-06   43.858     0.000     9.97e-05   0.000
Diameter_m              0.0003     2.64e-06   116.189    0.000     0.000     0.000
Longitude               -3.854e-05  1.04e-05   -3.695     0.000     -5.9e-05   -1.81e-05
Latitude                -8.996e-05  1.35e-05   -6.648     0.000     -0.000     -6.34e-05
Lifetime_production_kWh -2.596e-10  1.6e-12   -162.214   0.000     -2.63e-10  -2.56e-10
=====
Omnibus:                10490.532   Durbin-Watson:           0.433
Prob(Omnibus):          0.000     Jarque-Bera (JB):        32326971.528
Skew:                   10.734     Prob(JB):                 0.00
...
Notes:
[1] Standard Errors assume that the covariance matrix of the errors is correctly specified.
[2] The condition number is large, 2.07e+09. This might indicate that there are
strong multicollinearity or other numerical problems.

```

Figure A52: Summary of regression results of the wind turbine fleet of France.

```

=====
                        OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          Total      R-squared:                0.935
Model:                  OLS      Adj. R-squared:           0.934
Method:                 Least Squares  F-statistic:              3976.
Date:                   Wed, 19 Feb 2025  Prob (F-statistic):       0.00
Time:                   08:35:59   Log-Likelihood:           9488.6
No. Observations:      1675      AIC:                      -1.896e+04
Df Residuals:          1668      BIC:                      -1.893e+04
Df Model:               6
Covariance Type:       nonrobust
=====
                        coef      std err      t      P>|t|      [0.025      0.975]
-----
const                   0.0142      0.001     12.297     0.000     0.012     0.016
P_rated_kw              2.653e-06   9.92e-08   26.754     0.000     2.46e-06   2.85e-06
Hub_height_m            8.091e-05   4.36e-06   18.543     0.000     7.24e-05   8.95e-05
Diameter_m              0.0003     3.3e-06   76.078     0.000     0.000     0.000
Longitude               -0.0002     4.43e-05   -4.929     0.000     -0.000     -0.000
Latitude                -0.0004     2.12e-05   -16.816    0.000     -0.000     -0.000
Lifetime_production_kWh -2e-10      1.96e-12  -102.285   0.000     -2.04e-10  -1.96e-10
=====
Omnibus:                494.553     Durbin-Watson:           0.393
Prob(Omnibus):          0.000     Jarque-Bera (JB):        1553.008
Skew:                   1.476     Prob(JB):                 0.00
...
Notes:
[1] Standard Errors assume that the covariance matrix of the errors is correctly specified.
[2] The condition number is large, 4.91e+09. This might indicate that there are
strong multicollinearity or other numerical problems.

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Figure A53: Summary of regression results of the wind turbine fleet of Portugal.

Figure A54: Climate Change impacts plotted versus rated power, hub height, rotor diameter, long- and latitude, capacity factors and turbine age of onshore and offshore wind turbines in Belgium.

Figure A55: Climate Change impacts plotted versus rated power, hub height, rotor diameter, long- and latitude, capacity factors and turbine age of onshore and offshore wind turbines in Norway.

Figure A56: Climate Change impacts plotted versus rated power, hub height, rotor diameter, long- and latitude, capacity factors and turbine age of onshore and offshore wind turbines in Italy.

Figure A57: Climate Change impacts plotted versus rated power, hub height, rotor diameter, long- and latitude, capacity factors and turbine age of onshore and offshore wind turbines in Austria.

Figure A58: Climate Change impacts plotted versus rated power, hub height, rotor diameter, long- and latitude, capacity factors and turbine age of onshore and offshore wind turbines in Denmark.

Figure A59: Climate Change impacts plotted versus rated power, hub height, rotor diameter, long- and latitude, capacity factors and turbine age of onshore and offshore wind turbines in France.

Figure A60: Climate Change impacts plotted versus rated power, hub height, rotor diameter, long- and latitude, capacity factors and turbine age of onshore and offshore wind turbines in Portugal.

Figure A61: Feature importance of predictors in the Random Forest model, showing the relative contribution of each variable to the model's predictive power for Belgium (units: dimensionless).

Figure A62: Feature importance of predictors in the Random Forest model, showing the relative contribution of each variable to the model's predictive power for Norway (units: dimensionless).

Figure A63: Feature importance of predictors in the Random Forest model, showing the relative contribution of each variable to the model's predictive power for Great Britain (units: dimensionless).

Figure A64: Feature importance of predictors in the Random Forest model, showing the relative contribution of each variable to the model's predictive power for Austria (units: dimensionless).

Figure A65: Feature importance of predictors in the Random Forest model, showing the relative contribution of each variable to the model's predictive power for Denmark (units: dimensionless).

Figure A66: Feature importance of predictors in the Random Forest model, showing the relative contribution of each variable to the model's predictive power for France (units: dimensionless).

Figure A67: Feature importance of predictors in the Random Forest model, showing the relative contribution of each variable to the model's predictive power for Portugal (units: dimensionless).

Figure A68: Distribution of the impact on biodiversity of the European countries

Country	Mean	Min	Max	25th percentile	75th percentile
AT	1.10E-06	5.18E-09	2.15E-05	1.12E-07	8.15E-07
BE	9.74E-07	2.02E-08	1.66E-05	8.77E-08	7.68E-07
DK	1.59E-06	1.54E-08	2.24E-04	1.18E-07	4.82E-07
EE	9.94E-06	6.74E-08	2.78E-05	9.93E-07	1.49E-05
FR	1.07E-06	4.77E-09	5.75E-05	7.90E-08	4.32E-07
DE	6.60E-07	1.04E-09	3.97E-04	3.27E-08	2.77E-07
GR	1.29E-05	1.25E-08	5.36E-04	2.05E-07	5.68E-06
IE	2.62E-05	3.53E-08	3.64E-04	2.13E-06	2.71E-05
IT	2.45E-06	-6.07E-06	1.17E-04	2.73E-07	1.67E-06
LV	7.52E-07	2.09E-08	4.12E-06	6.28E-08	3.90E-07

LT	6.36E-07	2.56E-09	1.33E-05	4.19E-08	4.13E-07
LU	1.07E-07	3.86E-08	1.76E-07	7.54E-08	1.42E-07
NL	7.20E-07	1.72E-08	1.52E-05	6.72E-08	3.69E-07
NO	2.64E-04	6.81E-08	5.93E-03	8.03E-06	1.69E-04
PT	4.19E-07	1.94E-09	3.66E-06	7.67E-08	5.62E-07
ES	3.47E-06	-2.87E-04	1.78E-04	5.40E-08	2.26E-06
SE	1.98E-06	5.95E-10	1.68E-04	6.28E-08	9.20E-07
GB	3.17E-05	2.49E-08	1.57E-03	3.36E-07	1.41E-05
All	7.66E-06	-2.87E-04	5.93E-03	6.71E-08	9.13E-07

Table A23: Basic statistics of the impact on biodiversity of the European wind fleet (in PDF/turbine)

Figure A69: Impact of the Austrian wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0412= Central European mixed forests, PA0431= Pannonian mixed forests, PA0445= Western European broadleaf forests, PA0501= Alps conifer and mixed forests.

Figure A70: Impact of the Belgian wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0402= Atlantic mixed forests, PA0445= Western European broadleaf forests.

Figure A71: Impact of the Estonian wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0436= Sarmatic mixed forests.

Figure A72: Impact of the French wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0402= Atlantic mixed forests, PA0445= Western European broadleaf forests, PA0501= Alps conifer and mixed forests, PA1215= Northeastern Spain and Southern France Mediterranean forests and PA1222= Tyrrhenian-Adriatic Sclerophyllous and mixed forests.

Figure A73: Impact of the German wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0402= Atlantic mixed forests, PA0405= Baltic mixed forests, PA0412= Central European mixed forests, PA0445= Western European broadleaf forests.

Figure A74: Impact of the Greek wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0404= Balkan mixed forests, PA0435= Rodope montane mixed forests, PA1201= Aegean and Western Turkey sclerophyllous and mixed forests, PA1205= Crete Mediterranean forests, PA1210= Illyrian deciduous forests and PA1217= Pindus Mountains mixed forests.

Figure A75: Impact of the Irish wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0409= Celtic broadleaf forests and PA0429= North Atlantic moist mixed forests.

Figure A76: Impact of the Italian wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0401= Apennine deciduous montane forests, PA0432= Po Basin mixed forests, PA0501= Alps conifer and mixed forests, PA1211= Italian sclerophyllous and semi-deciduous forests, PA1218= South Apennine mixed montane forests, and PA1222= Tyrrhenian-Adriatic Sclerophyllous and mixed forests.

Figure A77: Impact of the LV wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0436= Sarmatic mixed forests.

Figure A78: Impact of the Lithuanian wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0412= Central European mixed forests and PA0436= Sarmatic mixed forests.

Figure A79: Impact of the Luxembourg wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0445= Western European broadleaf forests.

Figure A80: Impact of the Dutch wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0402= Atlantic mixed forests.

Figure A81: Impact of the Norwegian wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0436= Sarmatic mixed forests, PA0520= Scandinavian coastal conifer forests, PA0608= Scandinavian and Russian taiga, PA1106= Kola Peninsula tundra and PA1110= Scandinavian Montane Birch forest and grasslands.

Figure A82: Impact of the Portuguese wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0406= Cantabrian mixed forests, PA1209= Iberian sclerophyllous and semi-deciduous forests, PA1216= Northwest Iberian montane forests and PA1221= Southwest Iberian Mediterranean sclerophyllous and mixed forests.

Figure A83: Impact of the Spanish wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0406= Cantabrian mixed forests, PA1203= Canary Islands dry woodlands and forests, PA1208= Iberian conifer forests, PA1209= Iberian sclerophyllous and semi-deciduous forests, PA1212= Mediterranean acacia-argania dry woodlands and succulent thickets, PA1215= Northeastern Spain and Southern France Mediterranean forests, PA1216= Northwest Iberian montane forests, PA1219= Southeastern Iberian shrubs and woodlands, and PA1221= Southwest Iberian Mediterranean sclerophyllous and mixed forests.

Figure A84: Impact of the Swedish wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0405= Baltic mixed forests, PA0436= Sarmatic mixed forests, PA0608= Scandinavian and Russian taiga and PA1110= Scandinavian Montane Birch forest and grasslands.

Figure A85: Impact of the British wind turbines on biodiversity, according to their ecoregions. PA0409= Celtic broadleaf forests, PA421= English Lowlands beech forests, PA0429= North Atlantic moist mixed forests and PA503= Caledon conifer forests.

Figure A86: Comparison of climate change impacts of the onshore use cases considering different lifetimes.

Figure A87: Comparison of climate change impacts of offshore use cases considering different lifetimes.

Figure A88: Comparison of climate change impacts of offshore use cases considering transformers for wind turbine connection to the grid instead of buses.

Figure A89: Comparison of climate change impacts of onshore use cases considering transformers for wind turbine connection to the grid instead of buses.